

**University of
Sheffield**

**Using online support groups to explore the experiences of individuals with
dental anxiety**

MAHDY J M A N ALSHEMMARI

A thesis submitted in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Dental Public
Health

The University of Sheffield
School of Clinical Dentistry

September 2024

Acknowledgements

I would like to sincerely thank my supervisor, Professor Sarah Baker, for her support throughout this project. Her guidance, understanding, and encouragement made this journey much smoother.

I also extend my gratitude to my English language tutor, Suzanne Priestley, for her invaluable support.

Additionally, I would like to thank Dr. Jennifer Kettle for her insightful support.

Abstract

Objectives: Online support groups have become a common avenue for social support amongst individuals with various health concerns. However, there has been limited systematic classification of the specific types of support sought by individuals with dental anxiety. The aim of this study was to assess the types and frequencies of social support sought within online support groups for dental anxiety.

Methods: Data were collected from a single online support group, and the content of the threads was analysed using the modified social support behavior code framework adapted by Algtewi, Owens, and Baker (2015).

Results: The results suggested that the most frequently sought types of support were sharing personal experiences (53.4%) and informational support (31.1%), followed by emotional support (9.8%). Other types included encouragement (3.0%), expressions of care (1.5%), expressions of gratitude (0.6%), network support (0.4%), and well-being information (0.2%). No statements sought tangible support, esteem support, or congratulations.

Conclusion: Online support groups can be advantageous for individuals with dental anxiety by providing a platform that enhances peer assistance and reduces stigma through features such as interactivity, asynchronicity, and anonymity. The current findings indicate that participation in online communities can increase self-efficacy, alleviate feelings of isolation through shared experiences, and offer a judgment-free space for those who have faced misunderstanding and guilt from close family members.

Table of Contents

Acknowledgements.....	2
Abstract.....	3
Table of Contents	4
Abbreviations.....	7
List of Tables.....	8
List of Figures.....	9
Declaration.....	9
Chapter 1: Introduction	10
Chapter 2: Literature review	12
2.1 Online support groups.....	12
2.1.1 Background and definitions.....	12
2.1.2 Demographics of online support group users	13
2.1.3 Factors influencing engagement with online support communities	13
2.1.4 The mechanism by which online support groups may be beneficial.....	14
2.1.5 Advantages of using online support groups compared to face-to-face groups	18
2.1.6 Disadvantages of using online support groups	18
2.1.7 Ethical considerations in internet research	18
2.1.7.1 Privacy and autonomy.....	19
2.1.7.2 Consent	19
2.1.7.3 Harm	19
2.2 Dental anxiety	20
2.2.1 Definitions of dental fear, anxiety, and phobia	20
2.2.2 Prevalence of dental anxiety.....	20
2.2.3 The mechanisms by which dental anxiety develops.....	23
2.2.4 Sociodemographic, socioeconomic status, and cultural factors influencing dental anxiety	24
2.2.5 Causes of dental anxiety	27
2.2.6 Impact of dental anxiety on the quality of life of adults.....	44
2.2.7 Impact of dental anxiety on society.....	51

2.2.8	Impact of dental anxiety on dental team and providers	53
2.2.9	Online support groups for dental anxiety	53
2.3	Social support.....	57
2.3.1	Definitions	57
2.3.2	Components of social support	58
2.3.2.1	Social embeddedness	58
2.3.2.2	Perceived support.....	58
2.3.2.3	Enacted support.....	58
2.3.3	Theories of social support.....	59
2.3.3.1	The direct effect of social support.....	59
2.3.3.2	The buffering effect of social support.....	59
2.3.4	Types of social support	60
2.4	Rationale for the current research	63
2.5	Aim of the research	65
2.6	Objectives of the research	65
Chapter 3: Methodology		66
3.1	Introduction.....	66
3.2	Method	66
3.2.1	Rationale for the method	67
3.3	Inclusion and exclusion criteria	67
3.3.1	Online support groups selection	67
3.3.1.1	Rationale for groups selection	68
3.3.2	Threads selection	70
3.3.2.1	Rationale for threads selection.....	71
3.4	Ethical considerations	72
3.5	Data collection	73
3.5.1	Rationale for selecting 25 threads per even month of 2022, 2023, and 2024	73
3.6	Data analysis	74
3.6.1	Rationale for choosing content analysis over other methodological approaches	74
3.7	Coding.....	74

3.7.1	Rationale for choosing the modified version of the social support behavior code	75
3.8	Pilot study	76
Chapter 4: Results	77
4.1	Types and frequencies of social support sought.....	77
4.1.1	Seeking informational support.....	79
4.1.2	Seeking wellbeing information.....	81
4.1.3	Seeking emotional support	82
4.1.4	Seeking esteem support	83
4.1.5	Seeking network support	83
4.1.6	Seeking tangible support	84
4.1.7	Sharing personal experiences	84
4.1.8	Expression of gratitude	86
4.1.9	Congratulations.....	87
4.1.10	Expression of care	87
4.1.11	Encouragement	88
4.2	Summary of key findings.....	89
Chapter 5: Discussion	90
5.1	What online support groups are available for individuals with dental anxiety? 90	
5.2	What types and frequencies of social support are sought in online support groups for dental anxiety?.....	90
5.3	Study limitations	97
5.4	Study strengths	99
Chapter 6: Conclusion and recommendations	101
6.1	Conclusion	101
6.2	Recommendations.....	101
6.2.1	Future research	102
6.2.2	Future practice/policy development	104
References	106

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
DA	Dental Anxiety
MDAS	Modified Dental Anxiety Scale
OHIP-14	Oral Health Impact Profile-14
OHRQoL	Oral Health-Related Quality of Life
OSG	Online Support Group
QoL	Quality of Life
SSBC	Social Support Behavior Code

List of Tables

Table 1: Factors driving engagement with online support groups.....	13
Table 2: Mechanisms by which online support groups provide benefits.....	14
Table 3: Estimated prevalence of dental anxiety amongst adults across different countries.....	21
Table 4: Theories explaining the mechanisms behind dental anxiety.....	23
Table 5: Sociodemographic, socioeconomic status, and cultural factors influencing dental anxiety	24
Table 6: Individual-related factors contributing to dental anxiety.....	28
Table 7: Provider-related factors contributing to dental anxiety	35
Table 8: Procedure-related factors contributing to dental anxiety	36
Table 9: Environmental-related factors contributing to dental anxiety	38
Table 10: Genetic-related factors contributing to dental anxiety.....	42
Table 11: Impact of dental anxiety on the quality of life of adults	45
Table 12: Impact of dental anxiety on society	52
Table 13: Impact of dental anxiety on dental team and providers	53
Table 14: Studies on online support groups for dental anxiety.....	54
Table 15: Social support behavior code (Cutrona and Suhr, 1992)	60
Table 16: Modified social support behavior code for support-seeking (Coursaris and Liu, 2009)	62
Table 17: List of online support groups categorised by location: United Kingdom, United States, and unspecified.....	70
Table 18: Modified social support behavior code for support-seeking (Algtewi, Owens, and Baker, 2015).....	75
Table 19: Distribution of social support types sought per thread in the 271 threads...	77
Table 20: Types and frequencies of social support sought across all 271 threads	78

List of Figures

Figure 1: Application of exclusion criteria for selecting online support groups 69

Figure 2: Application of exclusion criteria for selecting support-seeking threads 72

Declaration

I, the author, confirm that the Thesis is my own work. I am aware of the University's Guidance on the Use of Unfair Means (www.sheffield.ac.uk/ssid/unfair-means). This work has not been previously been presented for an award at this, or any other, university.

Chapter 1: Introduction

Online support groups (OSGs) are internet-based tools enabling synchronous and asynchronous interactions amongst individuals with shared experiences (Zahra *et al.*, 2024). They can be accessed via various platforms, including discussion forums, social media, blogs, and chat rooms (Anawade, Sharma, and Gahane, 2024).

Discussion forums, also known as bulletin boards, allow users to post and respond to messages asynchronously (Marshall *et al.*, 2024). They offer benefits such as geographical flexibility, cost-free participation, and anonymity, which encourages open sharing (Rayland and Andrews, 2023; Wright *et al.*, 2024). These forums are valuable for those seeking information, advice, and emotional support, particularly for health issues like dental anxiety (DA) (Buchanan and Coulson, 2007).

DA is a heightened fear of dental treatment, affecting 12.4% of adults globally (Silveira *et al.*, 2021a). Those with DA often delay or avoid dental visits, leading to worse oral health and reduced quality of life (QoL) (Winkler *et al.*, 2023). This avoidance impacts individuals' well-being, societal productivity, and dental team efficiency (Armfield and Marek, 2017; Tizzoni *et al.*, 2020). Factors contributing to DA include past painful experiences, general anxiety, and lack of social support (Costa *et al.*, 2018; Song, Luzzi and Brennan, 2023).

Theories on social support, such as the direct effect and buffering effect hypotheses, highlight how social interactions can aid in stress management, whilst a lack of support can heighten isolation (Cohen and Wills, 1985; Rook, 1985). OSGs can facilitate these interactions in a virtual space (Pearce *et al.*, 2022). Studies have examined social support in OSGs for DA, finding that users seek help, share fears, and experience reduced anxiety (Buchanan and Coulson, 2007; Coulson and Buchanan, 2007). Types of support offered include emotional and informational support, with less emphasis on esteem, network, and tangible support (Abusulttan, 2020). Yet, there remains a gap in research regarding the specific types of social support that individuals seek within a structured classification.

Understanding the multifaceted nature of DA is crucial for improving dental care and preventing associated health issues (Valastro, Bono, and Gurenlian, 2024; Chalmers *et al.*, 2017). Poor oral health is also linked to mental health disorders (Halonen *et al.*, 2018; Kisely, 2016).

The present research therefore aims to fill this gap by conducting internet-mediated research of naturally occurring data from OSGs for DA through qualitative and quantitative content analysis in order to explore the types and frequencies of social support sought. Internet-mediated research can capture human behaviours that mirrors everyday situations and is advantageous for avoiding challenges associated with face-to-face interviews (The British Psychological Society, 2021; Chew and Gunasekeran, 2021; Kleinheksel *et al.*, 2020; Gheyle and Jacobs, 2017; Callen and Oxlad, 2024; Krippendorff, 2019).

The thesis is organised into six chapters. Chapter 2 introduces OSGs, detailing their background, communication tools, user demographics, and benefits, whilst comparing them with in-person support groups and addressing ethical considerations. It also examines DA, including its definitions, prevalence, causes, impacts, and the role of OSGs in managing it, before discussing social support theories and the research's rationale and objectives. Chapter 3 outlines the research design, including the study's rationale, criteria for selecting OSGs and threads, ethical considerations, and data collection and analysis methods, with a focus on content analysis and coding. Chapter 4 presents the findings from the content analysis, detailing the types and frequencies of social support sought. Chapter 5 interprets these results, examines the relevance of OSGs for DA, and discusses the study's limitations and strengths. Chapter 6 summarises the findings and offers recommendations for future research and practice, concluding with a comprehensive reference list.

Chapter 2: Literature review

The literature review begins with an exploration of OSGs, exploring their emergence, definitions, demographics, engagement factors, benefits, drawbacks, and ethical issues in internet-based research. It then addresses DA, including its definitions, prevalence, mechanisms, sociodemographic factors, causes, and impact on QoL, society, and dental professionals. The review also discusses the role of OSGs in managing DA and concludes with an examination of social support, including its definitions, components, theoretical frameworks, and types.

2.1 Online support groups

This section examines the concept and role of OSGs along with the ethical considerations involved.

2.1.1 Background and definitions

The rise of the internet has led to the growth of online communities, where individuals engage in discussions, form relationships, and share experiences (Szeto *et al.*, 2021; Hwang and Foote, 2021). OSGs are digital spaces for exchanging information and support, accessible through platforms like Reddit, Facebook, blogs, Twitter, and virtual reality (Anawade, Sharma, and Gahane, 2024). They facilitate both synchronous interactions (e.g., chat rooms) and asynchronous interactions (e.g., discussion forums) (Zahra *et al.*, 2024). Discussion forums, which allow anonymous message sharing within organised threads, are a key component of OSGs (Marshall *et al.*, 2024; Wright *et al.*, 2024). The widespread use of OSGs reflects their flexibility and value in addressing various health and life challenges (Yuchao, Ying, and Liao, 2021; Da Moura Semedo, Bath, and Zhang, 2023).

In the current study, the term OSGs specifically refers to online discussion forums, which are classified as asynchronous platforms as defined above.

2.1.2 Demographics of online support group users

Several socio-demographic factors influence engagement with OSGs. Participation spans various age groups, with some studies showing higher female engagement (Daynes-Kearney and Gallagher, 2023), whilst others report more male involvement (Gilbert *et al.*, 2022). Higher education and income levels are linked to greater activity, though ethnic minorities participate less frequently (Walsh and Al Achkar, 2021). Engagement is also higher amongst individuals with conditions like depression, anxiety, cancer, or those with stigmatised illnesses (Coulson, 2018). As of 2022, 63% of global internet users were female, with young people aged 15-24 showing the highest internet usage (Statista, 2024).

2.1.3 Factors influencing engagement with online support communities

There are several factors that drive individuals to engage with OSGs, as outlined in Table 1.

Table 1: Factors driving engagement with online support groups

Factor	Description
Limited access to traditional support networks	Individuals may have limited face-to-face support due to a lack of knowledgeable people in their social network or because their condition is rare or not well-understood (Coulson and Buchanan, 2022).
Health-related stigma	Users often face stigma or embarrassment about their condition, leading them to seek support in a non-judgmental environment like online communities (Strand, Eng, and Gammon, 2020).

Perceived similarity and credibility	Users are drawn to online support communities because they perceive other members to have similar experiences and believe their support is credible and understanding (Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2019).
Convenience and features of online communication	Online communities can offer accessibility, anonymity, and convenience, enabling users to engage at their own pace and comfort level without geographical or time constraints (Rayland and Andrews, 2023).

2.1.4 The mechanism by which online support groups may be beneficial

The mechanisms by which OSGs can offer benefits are illustrated through five theoretical perspectives, as summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: Mechanisms by which online support groups provide benefits

Theory	Mechanism
Optimal matching theory	<p>According to this theory, support groups are most beneficial when the support provided aligns with the specific needs of users, based on four dimensions of a stressor as described by Cutrona and Russell (1990): desirability, controllability, duration of consequences, and life domain.</p> <p>Desirability refers to the extent to which the stressor generates intense negative emotions. For stressors that are highly undesirable and evoke strong negative feelings, emotional support is often most</p>

effective. This type of support helps individuals cope with their distress through empathy and understanding.

Controllability relates to the degree of control an individual has over the stressor and its outcomes. For stressors perceived as controllable, such as making decisions about health or managing practical aspects of a situation, informational support is particularly beneficial. This support provides users with the knowledge and guidance necessary to manage their circumstances effectively. For instance, if a user seeks advice on managing a health condition, which fits the controllability dimension, and receives relevant information from fellow members, the support is considered an optimal match (Coulson, 2018).

Duration of consequences involves the length of time the effects of the stressor persist. For stressors with long-term effects, such as chronic conditions or ongoing life challenges, instrumental support is crucial. This type of support includes practical help and resources that address the persistent demands of the stressor, easing the burden over time.

Life domain pertains to the specific area of life affected by the stressor, such as personal or professional domains. Support that aligns with the affected life domain is more effective. For example, work-related stressors may benefit from professional advice or career counselling, whilst personal stressors might require support focused on personal relationships and self-care.

This alignment can help in addressing users' precise requirements through online support groups and can lead to more positive outcomes (Da Moura Semedo, Bath, and Zhang, 2023).

<p>Uses and gratifications model</p>	<p>According to this model, users turn to online support groups to satisfy specific needs and desires (Falgoust <i>et al.</i>, 2022).</p> <p>Unlike traditional media, the internet can offer interactive and customisable content, including interactivity, where the roles of broadcaster and receiver are blended; demassification, which allows users to select content that interests them; asynchronicity, enabling access to content at any time, globalisation, providing access to a wide range of international content; dialogicity, fostering two-way communication; and equality, giving a platform to diverse voices (Huang, Wu, and Huang, 2017).</p> <p>Online support groups can allow users to choose and engage with content that directly addresses their informational and emotional needs, providing a sense of control over the support they receive (Naslund <i>et al.</i>, 2020).</p>
<p>Social comparison theory</p>	<p>According to this theory, individuals seek accurate self-evaluations by comparing themselves with others (Festinger, 1954).</p> <p>In the context of online communities, users may compare their own health status or coping strategies with those of other members, thus gain valuable insights into their own condition and coping mechanisms (Malloch, Zhang, and Qian, 2023). However, it may also have negative effects if users engage in unfavourable comparisons that lead to feelings of inadequacy or distress (Lee, 2020).</p>
<p>Empowerment</p>	<p>According to this theory, empowerment is achieved through users gaining efficacy, greater control, and social justice by actively participating in the community (Zimmerman, 1995).</p>

	<p>This active engagement in online support groups can allow individuals to exchange information, offer support, share experiences, and receive recognition, which enhances their confidence and social well-being (Liu and Wang, 2021).</p> <p>Involvement often leads users to feel more informed and optimistic about their health conditions, thereby developing a stronger sense of self-efficacy (Vainauskiene and Vaitkiene, 2021).</p>
<p>Affordance theory</p>	<p>According to this theory, users interact with the features of online support groups based on how they perceive their potential benefits (Gibson, 1986).</p> <p>Key affordances include self-presentation, which refers to the ability to exercise autonomy over discussing personal experiences and disclosing information within the community; connection, which means the ability to interact with others to gain mutual support and reduce feelings of isolation; exploration, which involves learning about one's condition and developing coping strategies; narration, which entails sharing and reading about personal experiences to enhance understanding; and adaptation, which relates to adjusting engagement based on individual needs and circumstances (Coulson, Bullock, and Rodham, 2017).</p> <p>These interactions can help manage health conditions and reduce feelings of isolation (Dodemaide <i>et al.</i>, 2021).</p>

2.1.5 Advantages of using online support groups compared to face-to-face groups

OSGs can offer several advantages over face-to-face meetings, including 24/7 access from any location, allowing individuals with busy schedules to seek support at their convenience (Coulson and Buchanan, 2022). Their asynchronous nature lets users reflect before responding, and anonymity encourages open discussions on sensitive topics (Eklund *et al.*, 2021). OSGs also facilitate easier self-disclosure (Pan *et al.*, 2020) and offer diverse, cost-effective peer support to a broad audience (Friedman *et al.*, 2018). Similar to offline groups, they promote social connectedness, reduce stigma, and support empowerment and recovery (Strand, Eng, and Gammon, 2020).

2.1.6 Disadvantages of using online support groups

Despite their benefits, OSGs have limitations. Access requires a device and internet, limiting availability (Coulson, 2018). In July 2024, 67.1% of the global population used the internet, with 63.7% active on social media (Statista, 2024). Online relationships can be temporary, and membership fluctuates frequently (Vriens and van Ingen, 2017). OSGs may also promote unhealthy behaviours and spread misinformation, though moderated boards help mitigate this (Chadwick, Hall, and Vaccari, 2023). Negative interactions can worsen emotions, and excessive use may reduce face-to-face contact, increasing depression and loneliness (Stieger, Lewetz, and Willinger, 2023).

2.1.7 Ethical considerations in internet research

OSGs can enable patients to support one another, share health information, and communicate with healthcare providers (Petric *et al.*, 2023). Consequently, more researchers utilise internet data to study health behaviours (Sugiura, Wiles, and Pope, 2017). Ethical guidelines for internet-mediated research emphasise respecting

autonomy, privacy, dignity, scientific integrity, social responsibility, and minimising harm (The British Psychological Society, 2021).

2.1.7.1 Privacy and autonomy

Online communication can blur the lines between public and private spaces (The British Psychological Society, 2021). Researchers must carefully assess potential harm in situations where online communication is ambiguous and determine the need for consent. Group moderators can guide researchers in studying online communities. Data confidentiality should be maintained, and copyright concerns must be addressed.

In the current study, data were unobtrusively collected from a public website and anonymised.

2.1.7.2 Consent

Obtaining consent in online research is challenging without personal contact. Researchers recommend adapting consent procedures to online environments (Burles and Bally, 2018), and some suggest negotiating consent with group owners (Harris *et al.*, 2024). Consent must be valid, easily understandable, and allow participants to withdraw easily (The British Psychological Society, 2021).

In the present study, consent was obtained from group moderators.

2.1.7.3 Harm

Researchers must protect participants from harm by ensuring consent, anonymity, and confidentiality (The British Psychological Society, 2021). When publishing quotes, they should evaluate potential risks and paraphrase content to prevent identification.

In this study, whilst participant characteristics were beyond control, anonymity was maintained, and paraphrasing ensured confidentiality. However, reduced control over participant characteristics affected the validity of the findings.

2.2 Dental anxiety

2.2.1 Definitions of dental fear, anxiety, and phobia

Previous studies have explored the differences between dental fear, anxiety, and phobia, although these terms are often used synonymously in the literature (Armfield, 2010a; Lutch, 1971; Sun *et al.*, 2024; Wong *et al.*, 2022).

Dental fear is an emotional response triggered by a specific, present stimulus encountered in a dental setting. In contrast, DA is a heightened state of apprehension that stems from the fear of potential distress associated with dental treatment, where the trigger is uncertain, unclear, or not present at the moment. On the other hand, dental phobia is a severe form of DA characterised by a persistent, intense, and unreasonable fear that is beyond voluntary control and does not respond to logical reasoning, typically focused on specific, easily identifiable objects or situations within the dental setting.

In the current thesis, the term DA specifically refers to a heightened state of apprehension, characterised by fear of potential distress from dental treatment, distinct from dental fear and dental phobia as defined above.

2.2.2 Prevalence of dental anxiety

Globally, dental fear is estimated to affect 15.3% of adults, DA 12.4%, and dental phobia 3.3% (Silveira *et al.*, 2021a).

A further search for DA prevalence amongst adults was conducted using two databases, Scopus and Web of Science, with a focus on geographic diversity across Africa, Asia, Europe, North America, Oceania, and South America. The selection criteria prioritised recent research from the past decade to capture current trends; however, some older studies were included due to the lack of recent research from certain countries. Search terms were utilised within the abstract field, involving *"dental anxiety" OR "dental fear" AND prevalence OR level* AND (country name) AND adult**. Asterisks were used for word variations, and quotation marks were applied for phrase searching. Only English-language papers were considered. When these databases yielded limited results, Google Scholar was used to find additional relevant studies. The results revealed significant regional variations in prevalence rates, as illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3: Estimated prevalence of dental anxiety amongst adults across different countries

Author, year	Location	Prevalence
Al-Shammari <i>et al.</i> , 2007	Kuwait	18.5%
Alyami <i>et al.</i> , 2020	Saudi Arabia	36.4%
Astrom, Agdal, and Sulo, 2022	Norway	24.5%
Bhatt <i>et al.</i> , 2018	India	81.2%
Chanpong, Haas, and Locker, 2005	Canada	5.5%
Cheung <i>et al.</i> , 2022	Philippines	11.0%
Dikshit, Limbu, and Bhattarai, 2013	Nepal	36.7%
Dimitriou, Schmidt, and Li, 2024	United States	17.5%
Dou <i>et al.</i> , 2018	China	83.1%
El Hajj, Fares, and Abou-Abbas, 2021	Lebanon	31.5%
Erazo <i>et al.</i> , 2018	Chile	33.3%

Eroglu, Ataoglu, and Kucuk, 2016	Turkey	10.3%
Gremigni <i>et al.</i> , 2014	Italy	12.6%
Ha and Ye, 2019	South Korea	8.9%
Hassan <i>et al.</i> , 2022	Egypt	90.5%
Moore and Bering, 2017	Denmark	9.5%
Musalam <i>et al.</i> , 2021	Tanzania	80%
Nicolas <i>et al.</i> , 2007	France	13.5%
Obeidat, Alsa'di, and Taani, 2014	Jordan	15.1%
Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024	England	42%
Ogawa, Sago, and Furukawa, 2020	Japan	2.2%
Olawole <i>et al.</i> , 2019	Nigeria	47.7%
Oosterink, de Jongh, and Hoogstraten, 2009	Netherlands	24.3%
Pohjola <i>et al.</i> , 2014	Finland	5.4%
Ramseier <i>et al.</i> , 2023	Switzerland	13.3%
Rauch, 2019	Germany	58.4%
Saatchi <i>et al.</i> , 2015	Iran	58.8%
Silveira <i>et al.</i> , 2021b	Brazil	22.1%
Sitheeque <i>et al.</i> , 2014	Malaysia	3.5%
Sivaramakrishnan <i>et al.</i> , 2022	Bahrain	23.7%
Sukumaran, Taylor, and Thomson, 2020	New Zealand	13.3%
Svensson, Hakeberg, and Wide, 2016	Sweden	9.8%
Thomson <i>et al.</i> , 1996	Australia	14.9%

These differences may reflect cultural variations amongst populations. For instance, cultural norms in certain regions, such as some Asian and African countries, might discourage individuals from disclosing their anxiety, viewing it as a sign of weakness or embarrassment (Hamid *et al.*, 2018; Minja and Kahabuka, 2019).

Despite advancements in dentistry, prevalence of DA has remained relatively stable over many decades (Silveira *et al.*, 2021a).

2.2.3 The mechanisms by which dental anxiety develops

There are five theories explaining the mechanisms behind DA (Carter *et al.*, 2014). These theories are outlined in detail in Table 4.

Table 4: Theories explaining the mechanisms behind dental anxiety

Theory	Description
Pavlovian cognitive conditioning	Is the pathway of dental fear and anxiety most commonly used by patients, where previous painful dental experiences adversely affect an individual's future dental visits.
Informative pathway	Is an indirect route to severe dental anxiety, where fear of dental events is acquired through hearing about these experiences from others.
Vicarious conditioning	Is another indirect pathway to severe dental anxiety, where individuals develop it by observing the reactions of others undergoing dental treatment.
Verbal transmission/threat	Is the process of learning about dangerous or threatening information through verbal transmission or reading, without direct observation of a traumatic event.
Parental pathway	Is a scenario where a child's dental anxiety develops through exposure to a parent's fearful behavior, with a notably stronger effect when the behavior is exhibited by the mother.

2.2.4 Sociodemographic, socioeconomic status, and cultural factors influencing dental anxiety

This section examines how various sociodemographic, socioeconomic, and cultural factors contribute to DA. Table 5 describes these factors and their relationships with DA.

Table 5: Sociodemographic, socioeconomic status, and cultural factors influencing dental anxiety

Factor	Reference
<p>Age</p> <p>Younger adults have been associated with more risk of dental anxiety.</p> <p>In England, the prevalence of severe dental anxiety decreases with age, from 14% amongst those aged 16 to 24 years to 6% amongst those aged 75 and older (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024).</p>	<p>Astrom, Agdal, and Sulo, 2022; Cheung <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Muneer <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Murad, Ingle, and Assery, 2020; Musalam <i>et al.</i>, 2021; Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024; Saheer <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Sukumaran, Taylor, and Thomson, 2020</p>

<p>Cultural background</p> <p>Ethnicity and religion can influence dental anxiety, with coping mechanisms and expressions varying across cultures (Minja and Kahabuka, 2019). Societies with cultures that emphasise self-control, emotional restraint, and adherence to social norms, tend to report higher levels of dental anxiety. Non-white individuals in Southern Brazil have been associated with more risk of dental anxiety (Silveira <i>et al.</i>, 2021b).</p>	<p>Kumari, Sharma, and Raj, 2023</p>
<p>Education</p> <p>Lower educational levels have been associated with more risk of dental anxiety.</p>	<p>Astrom, Agdal, and Sulo, 2022; Cheung <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Murad, Ingle, and Assery, 2020; Ramseier <i>et al.</i>, 2023</p>
<p>Gender</p> <p>Females have been associated with more risk of dental anxiety compared to males. Cultural factors may contribute to this observation, as some cultures might find it more acceptable for women to openly express fear, whilst men may be culturally encouraged to hide their anxiety (Silveira <i>et al.</i>, 2021a). Additionally, female reproductive hormones may play a role in this difference (Costa <i>et al.</i>, 2018).</p>	<p>Al-Shammari <i>et al.</i>, 2007; Armfield, 2010b; Armfield, Spencer, and Stewart, 2006; Astrom, Agdal, and Sulo, 2022; Cheung <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Costa <i>et al.</i>, 2018; Eroglu, Ataoglu, and Kucuk, 2016;</p>

	<p>Liinavuori <i>et al.</i>, 2019; Muneer <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Murad, Ingle, and Assery, 2020; Musalam <i>et al.</i>, 2021; Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024; Olawole <i>et al.</i>, 2019; Pohjola <i>et al.</i>, 2014; Ramseier <i>et al.</i>, 2023; Saheer <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Samami, Farrahi, and Alinia, 2024; Silveira <i>et al.</i>, 2021b; Sivaramakrishnan <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Sukumaran, Taylor, and Thomson, 2020</p>
<p>Income</p> <p>Individuals with lower income levels have been associated with a higher risk of dental anxiety.</p> <p>Severe dental anxiety was less prevalent amongst individuals in the highest and second-highest income quintiles in England, both at 10%, and slightly more prevalent amongst those in lower-income households, with the highest</p>	<p>Muneer <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Ramseier <i>et al.</i>, 2023; Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024; Sukumaran, Taylor,</p>

prevalence of 14% in the lowest and second-lowest income quintiles (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024).	and Thomson, 2020
<p>Neighbourhood deprivation</p> <p>In the most deprived areas, 15% of adults report severe dental anxiety, compared to 9% in the two least deprived areas in England.</p>	Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024

However, some studies have reported contrasting findings. For example, Dimitriou, Schmidt, and Li (2024) and Hamid *et al.* (2018) found no significant associations between DA and factors such as age, gender, or education, which contradicts the observations in Table 5 indicating that younger adults, females, and those with lower educational levels are at a higher risk of DA. Additionally, Astrom, Agdal, and Sulo (2022), Dimitriou, Schmidt, and Li (2024) and Silveira *et al.* (2021b) found no association between income and DA. Moreover, Samami, Farrahi, and Alinia (2024) found that older adults experienced more DA compared to younger adults. Furthermore, Muneer *et al.* (2022) and Musalam *et al.* (2021) found that individuals with a higher level of education experienced more DA than those with a lower level of education. These opposing results may contribute to the complexity of sociodemographic and socioeconomic factors influencing DA.

2.2.5 Causes of dental anxiety

DA can arise at any stage of life, from childhood to adulthood, and is influenced by a variety of factors (Locker *et al.*, 1999).

The causes of DA are complex and multifaceted, involving individual-related, provider-related, procedure-related, environmental-related, and genetic-related factors. These factors are listed in Tables 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10, respectively.

Table 6: Individual-related factors contributing to dental anxiety

Factor	Reference
Agoraphobia	Locker, Poulton, and Thomson, 2001; Pohjola <i>et al.</i> , 2011
Alcohol use	Pohjola <i>et al.</i> , 2014
Any trauma	Kumari, Sharma, and Raj, 2023
Bullying Being called negative names, marginalised, threatened, or bullied by fellow students or coworkers over a long period of time has been associated with a higher risk of dental anxiety.	Nermo <i>et al.</i> , 2021
Cannabis dependence	Locker, Poulton, and Thomson, 2001
Childhood neglect/failure of care Not receiving necessities such as food, clothing, protection, and care/love from parents or caregivers has been associated with a higher risk of dental anxiety.	Nermo <i>et al.</i> , 2021

<p>Conduct disorder</p>	<p>Locker, Poulton, and Thomson, 2001</p>
<p>Dental trauma or previous negative dental experience during childhood, adolescence, or adulthood</p> <p>Experiences of pain through dental treatment at any of these life stages have been identified in most studies as a primary source of dental anxiety. This includes other unpleasant, unsatisfactory, and distressing dental experiences. Adults whose fears originated in childhood or early adolescence tend to be less trusting and more hostile toward dentists compared to others (Armfield and Marek, 2017).</p>	<p>Armfield, 2010c; Cheung <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Davey, 1989; Dimitriou, Schmidt, and Li, 2024; El Hajj, Fares, and Abou-Abbas, 2021; Hassan <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Lauth, 1971; Locker <i>et al.</i>, 1999; Locker, Shapiro, and Liddell, 1996; Sivaramakrishnan <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Nermo <i>et al.</i>, 2021; Kumari, Sharma, and Raj, 2023; Olawole <i>et al.</i>, 2019; Ramseier <i>et al.</i>, 2023</p>

<p>Depression</p>	<p>Locker, Poulton, and Thomson, 2001; Pohjola <i>et al.</i>, 2011; Shet <i>et al.</i>, 2013</p>
<p>Disabilities</p> <p>Prevalence of dental anxiety was estimated at 43.2% amongst individuals with disabilities in a special needs clinic in the U.S. (Kinoshita-Byrne, and Getz, 2002). Those with psychological disabilities reported the highest levels of fear, followed by individuals with medical disabilities, motor disabilities, and cognitive disabilities. In that study, cognitive disabilities included Alzheimer’s disease, autism, Down syndrome, and mental retardation. Motor disabilities encompassed cerebral palsy, multiple sclerosis, seizure disorder, spinal cord injury, and traumatic brain injury. Psychological disabilities comprised neurosis and psychosis. Medical disabilities included blood-lymphatic disorders, bone, joint, or muscle disorders, cardiac disorders, cancer, endocrine disorders, genito-urinary disorders, gastro-intestinal disorders, pulmonary disorders, sensory disorders, and vascular disorders.</p> <p>Moreover, a study on individuals with intellectual disabilities found that they are at a higher risk for dental anxiety, with prevalence rates ranging from 24% to 28%, particularly amongst those with more severe levels of intellectual disabilities (Kildahl <i>et al.</i>, 2024). Additionally, Fallea, Zuccarello, and Cali (2016) propose that this heightened dental anxiety may be associated with limited psychological resources for managing stress and difficulties in cognitive areas such as memory, problem-solving, and planning.</p>	<p>Fallea, Zuccarello, and Cali, 2016; Kildahl <i>et al.</i>, 2024; Martin, Kinoshita-Byrne, and Getz, 2002</p>
<p>Dysthymia</p>	<p>Locker, Poulton, and Thomson,</p>

	2001; Pohjola <i>et al.</i> , 2011
Fear of betrayal	Appukuttan, 2016
Fear of blood-injury	Armfield, 2010c; Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Vika <i>et al.</i> , 2008
Fear of fainting	Vika <i>et al.</i> , 2008
Fear of choking and/or gagging	Appukuttan, 2016
Fear of pain	Cheung <i>et al.</i> , 2022; Dimitriou, Schmidt, and Li, 2024; Hassan <i>et al.</i> , 2022; Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Kumari, Sharma, and Raj, 2023
Fear of the unknown	Appukuttan, 2016; Nithya <i>et al.</i> , 2018
Feeling of loss of control or helplessness on the dental chair	Appukuttan, 2016; Kumari, Sharma, and Raj, 2023; Oosterink, de Jongh, and Aartman, 2009
Generalised anxiety/history of generalised anxiety	Costa <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Dimitriou, Schmidt, and Li, 2024; Pohjola <i>et al.</i> , 2011

<p>Lack of trust in dentists/staff</p>	<p>Song, Luzzi, and Brennan, 2023</p>
<p>Nausea during dental treatment</p>	<p>El Hajj, Fares, and Abou-Abbas, 2021; Oosterink, de Jongh, and Aartman, 2009</p>
<p>Obsessive compulsive disorder</p>	<p>Locker, Poulton, and Thomson, 2001</p>
<p>Oral health literacy</p> <p>Lack of awareness or knowledge regarding oral health issues and treatment processes has been associated with a higher risk of dental anxiety.</p>	<p>Musalam <i>et al.</i>, 2021; Shin, Braun, and Inglehart, 2013; Ramseier <i>et al.</i>, 2023; Samami, Farrahi, and Alinia, 2024; Strieder <i>et al.</i>, 2019</p>
<p>Panic disorder</p>	<p>Locker, Poulton, and Thomson, 2001; Pohjola <i>et al.</i>, 2011</p>
<p>Perceived oral health status</p> <p>Feelings of embarrassment about one's oral health status have been associated with a higher risk of dental anxiety.</p> <p>Adults in England who rated their oral health as good or very good reported severe dental anxiety at 8%, compared with 35% of adults who rated their</p>	<p>Hassan <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Kumari, Sharma, and Raj, 2023; Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024; Ramseier <i>et al.</i>,</p>

<p>oral health as bad or very bad (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024).</p>	<p>2023; Shin, Braun, and Inglehart, 2013; Silveira <i>et al.</i>, 2021b</p>
<p>Perception of body image</p> <p>Negative perceptions of body image have been linked to an increased risk of dental anxiety.</p>	<p>Appukuttan, 2016</p>
<p>Personality traits</p> <p>Neuroticism has been linked to higher dental anxiety, whilst conscientiousness has been associated with slightly lower dental anxiety. Extraversion, agreeableness, and openness have shown non-significant relationships with dental anxiety.</p>	<p>Appukuttan, 2016; Hamid <i>et al.</i>, 2018; Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Sammith Shetty, Shibani Shetty, and Swapna, 2023; Valdes-Stauber and Hummel, 2021</p>
<p>Previous experience of a dentist not using anaesthesia during childhood</p>	<p>Dimitriou, Schmidt, and Li, 2024</p>
<p>Previous experience of dental pain or dental caries during childhood</p>	<p>Kumari, Sharma, and Raj, 2023; Silveira <i>et al.</i>, 2021b; Svensson, Hakeberg, and Wide, 2018</p>

Previous experience of fainting or panic attacks during dental treatment	Armfield, 2010c; Locker, Shapiro, and Liddell, 1996
Previous experience of gagging or choking during dental treatment	Armfield, 2010c
Previous experience of root canal treatment However, Hamid and colleagues (2018) found no associations between dental anxiety and previous experiences of root canal treatment.	Wong and Lytle, 1991
Previous experience with intraoral injections during dental treatment	Armfield, 2010c; Olawole <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Previous traumatic medical treatment in hospital	Nermo <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Oosterink, de Jongh, and Aartman, 2009
Severe traffic accidents	Oosterink, de Jongh, and Aartman, 2009
Sexual abuse	Nermo <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Oosterink, de Jongh, and Aartman, 2009
Simple phobia	Locker, Poulton, and Thomson, 2001
Social phobia	Locker, Poulton, and Thomson,

	2001; Pohjola <i>et al.</i> , 2011
Tobacco use	Pohjola <i>et al.</i> , 2014
Tragic death of a loved one	Oosterink, de Jongh, and Aartman, 2009
Vicarious learning from fearful family members, hearing negative dental stories from friends and social media, or watching distressing scenes in movies	Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Oosterink, de Jongh, and Aartman, 2009; Wong and Lytle, 1991
Violence Exposure to being hit, kicked, beaten, robbed, or threatened with a firearm has been associated with a higher risk of dental anxiety.	Nermo <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Oosterink, de Jongh, and Aartman, 2009

Table 7: Provider-related factors contributing to dental anxiety

Factor	Reference
Angry dentist/staff	Hmud and Walsh, 2007
Bad manners	Hmud and Walsh, 2007
Communication techniques/skills	Hmud and Walsh, 2007

Condescending marks and bad communication skills contribute to a higher risk of dental anxiety.	
Unfriendly or unaccepting dentist/staff	Hmud and Walsh, 2007
Unsympathetic/non-supportive dentist/staff	Dimitriou, Schmidt, and Li, 2024; Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Kheir <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Musalam <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Nithya <i>et al.</i> , 2018

Table 8: Procedure-related factors contributing to dental anxiety

Factor	Reference
Excessive instrumentation in the mouth	Dimitriou, Schmidt, and Li, 2024
Fear of injection It was estimated that 25% of adults in England experience dental anxiety when they are about to receive a local anaesthetic injection (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024).	Armfield, 2010c; Cheung <i>et al.</i> , 2022; Davey, 1989; Hassan <i>et al.</i> , 2022; Kumari, Sharma, and Raj, 2023; Nithya <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024;

	Ramseier <i>et al.</i> , 2023; Sivaramakrishnan <i>et al.</i> , 2022
Fear of wrong/misdiagnosed treatment	Sivaramakrishnan <i>et al.</i> , 2022
Gag-inducing procedures	Hmud and Walsh, 2007
Long appointment time	Sivaramakrishnan <i>et al.</i> , 2022
Radiation/x-rays Certain dental x-rays, such as periapical radiographs, may trigger a gag reflex or cause discomfort (Eachempati <i>et al.</i> , 2019).	Appukuttan, 2016; Hassan <i>et al.</i> , 2022; Sivaramakrishnan <i>et al.</i> , 2022
Root canal treatment	Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Nithya <i>et al.</i> , 2018
Teeth cleaning, i.e., scaling and root planning It was estimated that 11% of adults in England experience dental anxiety when they are about to have their teeth scaled and polished (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024).	Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024; Sammith Shetty, Shibani Shetty, and Swapna, 2023
Teeth filling/sensation of the dental drill and crown preparation	Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Nithya <i>et al.</i> , 2018
Teeth extraction	Cheung <i>et al.</i> , 2022; Dimitriou, Schmidt, and Li, 2024; Hmud

	and Walsh, 2007; Nithya <i>et al.</i> , 2018
--	---

Table 9: Environmental-related factors contributing to dental anxiety

Factor	Reference
Dental waiting room layout, design and content	Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Sammith Shetty, Shibani Shetty, and Swapna, 2023
High cost of dental treatment	Armfield, 2010c; Ramseier <i>et al.</i> , 2023
<p>Homelessness</p> <p>Some homeless populations in Hungary do use mobile phones to access health-related websites and seek advice for addressing various issues, including depression, anxiety, self-harm, abuse, substance use, emotional challenges, insomnia, and stress (Rado <i>et al.</i>, 2022).</p> <p>Research on homeless Australians found that dental anxiety was more prevalent amongst homeless individuals, with a rate of 28.2%, compared to 16% in the general Australian population (Yokota <i>et al.</i>, 2020). Furthermore, dental anxiety in this group was linked to poor self-rated oral health, driven by feelings of embarrassment or shame.</p>	Yokota <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Yusuf, Golkari, and Kaddour, 2023

<p>Moreover, a study in London found that homeless individuals reported fear of accessing health services due to previous experiences of degrading treatment by healthcare professionals and administrative staff (Yusuf, Golkari, and Kaddour, 2023). Additionally, this population expressed embarrassment about their oral health and anxiety about the use of local anaesthetic, with some fearing needles due to past drug abuse, which found to exacerbate their dental anxiety.</p>	
<p>Household disability status</p> <p>Individuals living in households with a disability are approximately twice as likely to experience high dental anxiety, with a prevalence of 21.8%, compared to those from households without a disability, who have a prevalence of 10.6%.</p>	<p>CareQuest Institute for Oral Health, 2022</p>
<p>Lack of social support</p> <p>Social support can influence a person’s oral health-related quality of life by affecting their attitudes, health knowledge, practices, and self-efficacy (Wang <i>et al.</i>, 2023). On the other hand, lack of social support has been associated with affecting the well-being of individuals, which can result in a lack of trust in dentists and subsequently lead to dental anxiety (Song, Luzzi, and Brennan, 2023). Furthermore, this deficiency in social support can contribute to anxiety symptoms, which are linked to an increased risk of dental anxiety (Costa <i>et al.</i>, 2018). In another study, lack of social support has been linked to social withdrawal and avoidance of dental care, which can negatively impact self-respect and overall well-being (Abrahamsson <i>et al.</i>, 2002).</p> <p>In addition, Crawford, Hawker, and Lennon (1997) qualitatively evaluated a support group for individuals with dental anxiety who were hesitant to seek</p>	<p>Abrahamsson <i>et al.</i>, 2002; Abusulttan, 2020; Buchanan and Coulson, 2007; Buchanan, Coulson, and Malik, 2010; Costa <i>et al.</i>, 2018; Coulson and Buchanan, 2007; Crawford, Hawker, and Lennon, 1997; Song, Luzzi, and Brennan, 2023; Wang <i>et al.</i>, 2023</p>

<p>dental care in the United Kingdom. The study utilised semi-structured interviews conducted through group discussions, either face-to-face or by telephone, at a primary health care centre within the community. The sample included 14 members of the support group, and 13 of them were tracked through a course of treatment after attending the group. The findings indicated that participation in the support group was important in alleviating fears and negative beliefs about dental care. The monitored group, averaging 43 years in age and with an average of 9 years since their last dental visit, underwent a mean of 5 treatment visits with minimal missed appointments and showed a significant reduction in dental anxiety. The study concluded that the support group fostered empathy amongst members, increased trust in dental professionals, and boosted confidence in seeking treatment.</p> <p>Moreover, social support exchanged in online support groups appears to reduce dental anxiety (Abusulttan, 2020; Buchanan and Coulson, 2007; Buchanan, Coulson, and Malik, 2010; Coulson and Buchanan, 2007).</p>	
<p>Natural disaster</p>	<p>Oosterink, de Jongh, and Aartman, 2009</p>
<p>Sight of blood/fear of bleeding</p>	<p>Hassan <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Nithya <i>et al.</i>, 2018</p>
<p>Sight of needle</p>	<p>Armfield, 2010c; Agras, Sylvester, and Oliveau, 1969; Cheung <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Davey, 1989; Hassan <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Kumari, Sharma, and Raj, 2023; Nithya <i>et al.</i>, 2018; Ramseier <i>et al.</i>, 2023;</p>

	Sammith Shetty, Shibani Shetty, and Swapna, 2023; Sivaramakrishnan <i>et al.</i> , 2022; Vika <i>et al.</i> , 2008
Sounds of moaning patients	Hmud and Walsh, 2007
<p>Sounds of the dental drill and suction</p> <p>It was estimated that this causes dental anxiety in 28% of adults in England when they are about to have their tooth drilled (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024).</p>	<p>Cheung <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Ghaffar <i>et al.</i>, 2024; Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Kumari, Sharma, and Raj, 2023; Nithya <i>et al.</i>, 2018; Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024; Sammith Shetty, Shibani Shetty, and Swapna, 2023; Sivaramakrishnan <i>et al.</i>, 2022</p>
The smell of eugenol in dental materials/unpleasant smell of clinic area	Hmud and Walsh, 2007
<p>Waiting time at the dental clinic</p> <p>It was estimated that sitting in the waiting room causes dental anxiety in 12% of adults in England (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024).</p>	Hmud and Walsh, 2007; Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024
War trauma	Oosterink, de Jongh, and Aartman, 2009

White coat/sight of the dentist	Sivaramakrishnan <i>et al.</i> , 2022
Witnessing serious injury, killing, or sexual abuse	Nermo <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Oosterink, de Jongh, and Aartman, 2009
Witnessing a treatment of an extremely dentally anxious individual	Oosterink, de Jongh, and Aartman, 2009

Table 10: Genetic-related factors contributing to dental anxiety

Factor	Example
Genetic correlation between dental fear and fear of pain	Randall <i>et al.</i> (2016) conducted a family-based cohort study in the United States, specifically in rural Appalachia, involving 1,370 participants from 732 households. The study included individuals aged 11–74 years, with 827 females, and used the dental fear survey and the fear of pain questionnaire-9 to assess dental fear and fear of pain. The researchers employed a variance components framework to estimate heritability and genetic correlations using likelihood-based methods. The findings revealed a substantial genetic correlation between dental fear and fear of pain, with heritability estimates of 30% for dental fear and 34% for fear of pain. This study indicated that although dental fear and fear of pain are related, they may represent distinct phenotypes influenced by shared genetic factors. Notably, the study’s self-report instruments and the fact that the sample was drawn from a socioeconomically disadvantaged area may impact the generalisability of the findings to more diverse populations.

<p>Genetic loci associated with dental fear and anxiety</p>	<p>Zhou and colleagues (2022) conducted a genome-wide association study combined with meta-analysis, involving participants from four cohorts. Cohort 1 was a population-based cohort, Center for Oral Health Research in Appalachia 1, which included 1,144 individuals from northern Appalachian families, with participants aged 13 and older. This cohort comprised 124 adolescents aged 13 to 17 years, and 1,020 adults aged 18 to 74 years, including 723 females and 421 males. The analysis sample included 886 unrelated participants, with an additional 258 individuals related to one or more participants in the unrelated set, drawn from 700 households. Cohort 2 was a longitudinal cohort, Center for Oral Health Research in Appalachia 2, focusing on 1,164 adult women from West Virginia and southwest Pennsylvania, following them and their babies for up to 7 years. The study specifically examined the mothers, who had an average age of 29 years, ranging from 18 to 47 years. Cohort 3 was a cross-sectional cohort, consisting of 535 unrelated individuals with an average age of 63.1 years, ranging from 45 to 75 years. This cohort included 356 females and 179 males. Cohort 4 was a longitudinal birth cohort, Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children, which included 2,078 adolescents from Bristol, UK, who were assessed for dental anxiety at age 17.5 years. This cohort comprised 1,268 females and 810 males.</p> <p>Significant genetic loci associated with dental fear and anxiety were identified, including the NTSR1 gene, which is linked to avoidance behaviours and involved in neurotensin function (Yamada <i>et al.</i>, 2010), as well as DMRTA1 and FAM84A. NTSR1 has been associated with altered fear memory in mice, whilst DMRTA1 and FAM84A were associated with physiological arousal and avoidance subscales. Heritability estimates for dental fear and anxiety ranged from 23% to 59%. Gene enrichment analyses revealed that genetic loci associated with dental fear and anxiety are enriched for genes related to severe mental health conditions, such as schizophrenia, and neurocognitive disorders like autism. The study's</p>
--	---

<p>limitations include the reliance on self-report instruments, modest sample size for a genome-wide association study and meta-analysis, and the exclusion of environmental factors and comorbidities, which could affect the detection of genetic variants associated with high levels of dental anxiety. The authors stated that future research may benefit from larger sample sizes and the inclusion of diverse assessment methods to further elucidate the genetic underpinnings of dental anxiety.</p> <p>On the other hand, Lauth (1971) argues that familial resemblance is more likely due to the influence of modelling rather than direct genetic factors.</p>

Therefore, DA appears to be influenced by a combination of environmental, experiential, genetic, lifestyle, psychological, and social factors, making it difficult to pinpoint a single cause.

2.2.6 Impact of dental anxiety on the quality of life of adults

DA can significantly affect individuals' health and well-being. Research shows about 20% of those with DA avoid regular dental care, with 9% to 15% avoiding it entirely (Valastro, Bono, and Gurenlian, 2024), leading to worsening oral health (Armfield, 2010b; Saheer *et al.*, 2022). This decline can result in serious conditions like heart disease, diabetes, and oral cancers (Chalmers *et al.*, 2017; Sheiham *et al.*, 2015) and is linked to mental health issues such as anxiety and depression (Kisely, 2016; Halonen *et al.*, 2018).

The vicious cycle of dental fear exacerbates this issue: avoidance of care worsens oral health, leading to more invasive treatments and increased DA (Berggren and Meynert, 1984; Armfield, Stewart, and Spencer, 2007). In England, adults with DA showed irregular dental attendance patterns, with 22% of those attending only when in trouble reporting DA, compared to 12% of occasional attendees and 8% of regular check-up visitors (Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, 2024).

Table 11 illustrates the impact of DA on adults, highlighting how it contributes to a lower QoL.

Table 11: Impact of dental anxiety on the quality of life of adults

Impact	Example
Behavioural and emotional	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Appearance, including hiding the teeth when laughing or smiling (Hassan <i>et al.</i>, 2022) 2. Avoidance of certain types of appointments, such as root canal treatment, scaling, and surgery (Winkler <i>et al.</i>, 2023) 3. Avoidance of dental care, including avoidance of passing by a dental office (Sukumaran, Taylor, and Thomson, 2020) 4. Avoidance of hard-to-chew foods and those that cause sensitivity (Hassan <i>et al.</i>, 2022) 5. Avoiding people (Appukuttan, 2016) 6. Blushing (Appukuttan, 2016) 7. Confusion and stumbling over words (Aardal <i>et al.</i>, 2022) 8. Difficulty in maintaining a balanced emotional state without getting angry (Aardal <i>et al.</i>, 2022) 9. Excessive worrying (Appukuttan, 2016) 10. Failure to appear for appointments (Armfield and Marek, 2017) 11. Getting tongue-tangled (Appukuttan, 2016)

	<p>12. Hyperactivity (Appukuttan, 2016)</p> <p>13. Improve oral hygiene practices and invest in high-quality dental care products to avoid the need for dental treatments and prevent dental issues (Cohen, Fiske, and Newton, 2000). However, Winkler <i>et al.</i> (2023) found that dentally anxious individuals in Germany had a reduced frequency of tooth brushing.</p> <p>14. In a hurry (Appukuttan, 2016)</p> <p>15. Inattentiveness (Appukuttan, 2016)</p> <p>16. Irritation with delays (Appukuttan, 2016)</p> <p>17. Nervous habits (Appukuttan, 2016)</p> <p>18. Outburst of emotions (Appukuttan, 2016)</p> <p>19. Pacing (Appukuttan, 2016)</p> <p>20. Panicky (Appukuttan, 2016)</p> <p>21. Rapidly thumbing through magazines (Appukuttan, 2016)</p> <p>22. Sitting on the edge of the chair and leaning forward (Appukuttan, 2016)</p> <p>23. Walking or talking faster (Appukuttan, 2016)</p>
Decision-making	<p>1. Difficulty making well-reasoned treatment decisions (Armfield and Marek, 2017)</p> <p>2. Difficulty understanding symptoms (Armfield and Marek, 2017)</p>
Financial	<p>1. Increased cost due to missed appointments (Armfield and Marek, 2017)</p> <p>2. Increased cost for complex or emergency care (Armfield and Marek, 2017)</p>

<p>General health</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sleep disturbances, such as difficulty sleeping the night before a dental appointment and experiencing dreams or nightmares related to dental fears at times unrelated to the appointment (Aardal <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Ghaffar <i>et al.</i>, 2024)
<p>Oral health</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acute and/or chronic dental pain (Minja and Kahabuka, 2019) 2. Clenching or grinding of the teeth during wakefulness or sleep (Sammith Shetty, Shibani Shetty, and Swapna, 2023) 3. Discomfort or loss of oral function, including difficulties with chewing (Samami, Farrahi, and Alinia, 2024) 4. Missing teeth —A study found that adults who did not attend regular dental visits had nearly three times the risk of becoming edentulous compared to those who regularly attended dental appointments (Weintraub <i>et al.</i>, 2019) 5. Oral infections (Armfield and Marek, 2017) 6. Poor gum health and breathing odour (Saheer <i>et al.</i>, 2022) 7. Tooth decay (Delgado-Angulo <i>et al.</i>, 2015; Eitner <i>et al.</i>, 2006) 8. Untreated tooth decay (Sukumaran, Taylor, and Thomson, 2020)

Physiological	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Clearing the throat (Appukuttan, 2016) 2. Depth and speed of respiration (Appukuttan, 2016) 3. Dry mouth (Appukuttan, 2016) 4. Frequent urination (Appukuttan, 2016) 5. Hands unsteady (Appukuttan, 2016) 6. Holding things tightly (Appukuttan, 2016) 7. Increased heart rate (Ghaffar <i>et al.</i>, 2024) 8. Muscle tightness (Appukuttan, 2016) 9. Painful aching (Levin <i>et al.</i>, 2018) 10. Poor memory (Appukuttan, 2016) 11. Restlessness (Appukuttan, 2016) 12. Stiff posture (Appukuttan, 2016) 13. Strong startle response (Appukuttan, 2016) 14. Sweating of the palms of hands, forehead, and upper lip (Appukuttan, 2016) 15. Taste worse (Levin <i>et al.</i>, 2018) 16. Trouble pronouncing words (Levin <i>et al.</i>, 2018) 17. Uncomfortable to eat (Levin <i>et al.</i>, 2018)
Psychological	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Anticipatory fears, such as worrying about teeth falling apart (Locker, 2003), fears of losing teeth, fears of death, ruminating on what might happen whilst waiting for the appointment, and catastrophic thoughts about potential outcomes (Cohen, Fiske, and Newton, 2000) 2. Anxiety about seeking dental care and treatment (Armfield and Marek, 2017), constant thinking about the need to see a dentist, and psychological distress before and during dental visits (Kumar <i>et al.</i>, 2009) 3. Been embarrassed (Levin <i>et al.</i>, 2018) 4. Beliefs, including feelings of foolishness about being afraid of dental treatment, the fear that people will laugh if they share their

dental treatment fears (Ghaffar *et al.*, 2024; Locker, 2003), being perceived as foolish or weak by others, a lack of understanding or appreciation for their anxiety, feelings of stigmatisation, and a preference for extreme measures like tooth extraction over repeated dental visits (Cohen, Fiske, and Newton, 2000)

5. **Diet unsatisfactory (Levin *et al.*, 2018)**

6. **Difficult to relax (Levin *et al.*, 2018)**

7. **Heightened sensitivity to dental stimuli and/or anticipation of pain, such as the sight and sound of dental instruments, the smell of the clinic, and the vibration of the drill (Hassan *et al.*, 2022)**

8. **Negative feelings, such as low self-esteem and getting upset when people talk about having fillings or injections (Ghaffar *et al.*, 2024; Locker, 2003), along with feelings of vulnerability and a sense of losing control whilst in the dental chair (Armfield and Marek, 2017)**

9. **Traumatic memories, illustrated by the distressing recollection of past traumatic dental experiences that some individuals vividly replay (Cohen, Fiske, and Newton, 2000)**

<p>Social</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Annoyance when pressured into having dental treatment (Locker, 2003) 2. Avoidance of applying for jobs due to concerns about the condition of their teeth (Locker, 2003) 3. Disliking contact with people (Aardal <i>et al.</i>, 2022) 4. Difficulty in accompanying others, including the challenge of attending dental appointments with family members and concerns about transmitting anxiety to their children (Cohen, Fiske, and Newton, 2000) 5. Difficulty in performing leisure and daily activities, involving instances where dental anxiety caused individuals to withdraw from recreational events, such as a fishing competition, due to severe dental pain (Aardal <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Cohen, Fiske, and Newton, 2000) 6. Increased sick leave, with some individuals reporting a reduction in sick leave following successful treatment for their dental anxiety, suggesting that untreated dental anxiety may be associated with more frequent sick leaves (Hakeberg and Berggren, 1993) 7. Negative feedback from others, such as being told that fears of dental treatment are childish or ridiculous (Locker, 2003) 8. Negative personal relationships, where severe dental anxiety adversely affects the development and maintenance of close relationships with friends, partners, or family, particularly due to avoidance of dental appointments and discussions about dental care (Shet <i>et al.</i>, 2013) 9. Refusing social invitations due to concerns about the condition of their teeth (Locker, 2003) 10. Reluctance to meet new people due to the state of their teeth (Locker, 2003)
----------------------	--

	<p>11. Taboo, with many individuals preferring not to discuss their dental anxiety or dental care with others (Cohen, Fiske, and Newton, 2000), and they prefer to hide their fears of dental treatment from others (Locker, 2003)</p> <p>12. Work-related mood and performance impacts, including changes in mood and avoidance of social contact at work, as well as effects on job performance and promotion prospects due to dental pain and concerns about appearance and communication (Hassan <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Aardal <i>et al.</i>, 2022)</p> <p>13. Work-related social interactions, such as concealing feelings about dental anxiety, with some individuals feeling regret over revealing their anxiety to colleagues, which may be perceived as a weakness (Cohen, Fiske, and Newton, 2000)</p>
--	--

2.2.7 Impact of dental anxiety on society

As a result of delaying or avoiding dental treatment due to DA, individuals often experience unnecessary pain and suffering (Armfield, 2013). Society bears the cost of these delays, as detailed in Table 12.

Table 12: Impact of dental anxiety on society

Impact	Example
<p>Lost workdays and reduced productivity</p>	<p>A study in Australia estimated the indirect cost of missed work and reduced activity time due to dental conditions at \$808 million, averaging 1.56 hours per worker—1.27 hours missed and 0.29 hours of reduced activity (Australian Research Centre for Population Oral Health, 2012). Moreover, research in Japan found a 7.8% reduction in work performance associated with dental issues, including poor gum health (Sato <i>et al.</i>, 2022).</p> <p>Between 15% and 35% of the U.S. population experience lost workdays due to dental problems (Reisine and Miller, 1985), with an estimated 2.4 million workdays lost annually due to acute dental conditions (Adams <i>et al.</i>, 1999). Additionally, a study in the U.S. found that 25% of 2,541 employees reported work loss related to dental issues (Reisine, 1985). Furthermore, a national estimate in the U.S. indicated that 4% of adults aged 30 and older experienced reduced productivity due to dental problems, affecting approximately 7 million individuals who faced difficulties in job performance and school over the past year (Aldosari <i>et al.</i>, 2021).</p> <p>On top of that, in 2015, the global indirect cost of productivity losses from absences at work and school due to dental conditions was estimated at US\$187.61 billion (Peres <i>et al.</i>, 2019). Additionally, in a comparison of expenditures on various diseases amongst the 28 EU member states in 2015, dental diseases ranked third at €90 billion, following diabetes at €119 billion and cardiovascular diseases at €111 billion (Peres <i>et al.</i>, 2019).</p>

2.2.8 Impact of dental anxiety on dental team and providers

The impact of DA on dental teams and providers is significant, affecting various aspects of practice as outlined in Table 13.

Table 13: Impact of dental anxiety on dental team and providers

Impact	Reference
Financial impact due to missed or unfilled appointments	Alabdulkarim <i>et al.</i> , 2022; Davies <i>et al.</i> , 2016
Increased staff time and attention for fearful patients	Uziel <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Increased stress and fatigue	Johns and Jepsen, 2015; Pouradeli <i>et al.</i> , 2016; Toon <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Reduced job satisfaction	Emrani <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Goetz, Schuldei, and Steinhauser, 2018
Decreased patient compliance, reduced treatment success rates, and misdiagnosis	Eli, 1993; Moore and Brodsgaard, 2001; Tizzoni <i>et al.</i> , 2020

2.2.9 Online support groups for dental anxiety

Dentistry-related applications are becoming a popular means of accessing information (Khatoon, Hill, and Walmsley, 2013). For example, Dental Fear Central, which is an international non-commercial site from the UK, offers resources for addressing dental

fear and anxiety (Dental Fear Central, 2024). It features a moderated support forum, information on common dental fears, guides for finding a dentist, psychological strategies for overcoming DA, and advice for patients and professionals. The platform serves patients, dental students, and professionals globally.

A search for studies on OSGs for DA was performed within the abstract fields of Scopus and Web of Science, selecting all relevant studies regardless of date. Search terms included "*dental anxiety*" OR "*dental fear*" AND *online* OR *internet* AND *groups** OR "*support groups*" OR "*social support*" OR "*health-related*" OR *community* AND "*message board*" OR "*social media*" OR "*discussion forum*" AND *adults**. Only English-language papers were included. The search results from Scopus revealed one study by Buchanan, Coulson, and Malik (2010), whilst Web of Science revealed two studies: Buchanan and Coulson (2007) and Coulson and Buchanan (2007). Google Scholar was also used to find additional studies due to limited results from the initial databases, which revealed a study by Abusulttan (2020). The results of the search can be seen in Table 14.

Table 14: Studies on online support groups for dental anxiety

Author, year	Findings
Abusulttan, 2020	Abusulttan (2020) aimed to examine the types of social support offered within this group. The study analysed 115 messages using content analysis based on a modified social support behavior code by Coulson and Greenwood (2012). The study found that emotional support was the most prevalent at 85.3%, characterised by understanding and empathy through sharing similar experiences, such as previous dental appointments, traumatic childhood experiences, treatment avoidance, and coping strategies. For example, members discussed how their close family members could not understand their fears, leading to feelings of guilt. Informational support followed at 57.3%, providing information that could assess, evaluate, or explain the

	<p>situation faced by others, along with suggestions for coping or solving issues. Esteem support was observed at 46.9%, which involved complimenting members and appraising them for their courage or thanking them for their support. Tangible aid was the least common at 3.4%, reflecting messages that expressed a desire to help or do something practical for the recipient.</p>
<p>Buchanan and Coulson, 2007</p>	<p>Buchanan and Coulson (2007) aimed to explore how individuals with dental anxiety access and experience the Dental Fear Central forum through an online questionnaire involving 143 participants. They identified three main themes from the responses. The first theme, 'searching for help,' highlighted that participants frequently acknowledged specific dental problems requiring treatment, such as bleeding gums or decayed teeth, and described their fears of dentists and dental procedures as overwhelming barriers. Some members felt that these fears were insurmountable and were often too ashamed to discuss their irrational fears with family and friends. As a result, they sought information, advice, and support from the internet, often discovering online support groups like Dental Fear Central through web searches. The second theme, 'sharing fears,' revealed that most respondents found significant comfort in knowing they were not alone in their anxieties. Some participants felt isolated as a result of not knowing anyone in their immediate social circles who shared similar fears. The third theme, 'feeling empowered,' showed that participants felt empowered to confront their fears by accessing messages from others facing similar challenges and receiving guidance, support, and encouragement from the forum.</p>
<p>Buchanan, Coulson, and Malik, 2010</p>	<p>Buchanan, Coulson, and Malik (2010) aimed to examine the nature of individuals' experiences with dental anxiety through their posted threads using thematic analysis. They analysed 621 messages and identified seven themes. The first theme, 'I can still remember...', revealed that many individuals believed their anxiety and phobia stemmed from past experiences where they felt a lack of control, physical restraint, or insufficient compassion from dental staff, with some also feeling uneasy discussing pain relief with dentists. The second theme, 'I was ashamed to smile or laugh,' highlighted that participants often felt shame and embarrassment about their dental</p>

	<p>anxiety, feeling guilty about their fear of what others considered ordinary and experiencing anger and low self-esteem due to perceived changes in their appearance and mouth health. The third theme, 'this big dark secret I can't share with anyone,' showed that many members felt their close relations did not understand the severity of their anxiety, which exacerbated their fears. The fourth theme, 'I can't stand it anymore,' indicated that some participants were driven to join the support group by a strong desire to overcome their phobia, reaching a breaking point where confronting their fears seemed preferable to enduring ongoing pain. The fifth theme, 'I cross the street rather than walk past the dental surgery,' illustrated how fears and anxieties acted as significant barriers to seeking dental treatment, with some members experiencing severe pre-appointment anxiety and physical symptoms such as shaking and nausea. The sixth theme, 'talking to a computer is much easier,' emphasised the role of anonymity and shared experiences in facilitating openness and reducing embarrassment compared to face-to-face interactions, helping members feel less isolated and more encouraged to discuss their fears with others. The final theme, 'find a dentist that you are comfortable with,' involved members exchanging tips on finding suitable dentists, sharing experiential knowledge, and offering tangible assistance by providing information about dentists and reviewing dental surgery websites.</p>
<p>Coulson and Buchanan, 2007</p>	<p>Coulson and Buchanan (2007) aimed to explore the self-reported effectiveness of the Dental Fear Central forum in terms of perceived anxiety levels since accessing the group over an 8-week period in 2005, using an online questionnaire and the modified dental anxiety scale. The study involved 91 participants between the ages of 16 and 64, with an average age of 36.95 years. The majority of participants, 76.9%, were female. In terms of nationality, 54.9% were from the United States, 30.8% from the United Kingdom, 7.7% from Canada, 5.5% from Australia, and 1.1% from Germany. Regarding marital status, 26.4% were single, 51.6% were married, 17.6% were cohabiting with a partner, 2.2% were separated or divorced, and 2.2% were in a relationship but living separately. The authors asked participants whether their dental anxiety had decreased, using five categories of response: 'greatly lessened,' 'somewhat lessened,' 'stayed much the same,' 'somewhat increased,' and 'greatly increased.' The</p>

	results showed that 17 participants reported their anxiety had greatly lessened, 38 reported it had somewhat lessened, 34 reported it had stayed the same, 1 reported it had somewhat increased, and 1 reported it had greatly increased.
--	---

Nevertheless, none of these studies have systematically categorised the types of support sought by individuals in OSGs for DA. For instance, Buchanan and Coulson (2007) noted that users sought help and shared fears within these groups but did not categorise the types of support or measure their frequency, as they employed thematic analysis rather than content analysis. Content analysis can allow for structured categorisation and measurement of support types (Hale, 2019), as used by Abusulttan (2020) to classify the types of support offered. Consequently, a structured classification of the types of support sought in these groups remains lacking.

2.3 Social support

2.3.1 Definitions

The definition of social support is widely debated, with varying views on its nature and dimensions. Barrera, Sandler, and Ramsay (1981) define it as aid and assistance from multiple sources, including family, friends, and community, whilst Cohen and McKay (1984) emphasise its role in stress protection through interpersonal relationships.

The concept often overlaps with terms like social bond and social network, leading to confusion (Rook, 1985). Social support is distinct from social integration, focusing on relationship quality and function rather than quantity (Schwarzer and Rieckmann, 2002). It also involves interaction, obligation, and reciprocation (Schwarzer and Leppin, 1992, cited in Mittelmark, 1999).

The present study adopts Barrera, Sandler, and Ramsay's (1981) broader definition, as it aligns with the diverse support found in OSGs for DA.

2.3.2 Components of social support

Despite the proliferation of social support concepts, it has been classified into three broad components, each having a different relationship with health: social embeddedness, perceived social support, and enacted support (Barrera, 1986; National Cancer Institute, 2020).

2.3.2.1 Social embeddedness

Social embeddedness or social integration is the frequency of an individual's interactions with others in their social network, including friends, family, and community members (National Cancer Institute, 2020). It has been linked to physical health outcomes such as heart disease and mortality (Barrera, 1986). This component is not necessary for the current study, which focuses on seeking social support rather than the frequency of interactions within a social network.

2.3.2.2 Perceived support

Perceived support, also known as functional support, is the belief that individuals capable of providing help will offer useful assistance during hard times (Barrera, 1986). This component is of particular interest in the current project, as the focus is on seeking social support.

2.3.2.3 Enacted support

Enacted support or received support is a specific form of assistance, such as offering reassurance or advice, provided by individuals during difficult times (Barrera, 1986). Whilst enacted support plays a crucial role in helping individuals cope with

challenges, this component is not the primary focus of the current study, which concentrates on seeking social support rather than the support already received.

2.3.3 Theories of social support

Two key theories explain the impact of social support on health: the direct effect and buffering effect theories (Barrera, 1986; Cohen, Gottlieb, and Underwood, 2000). The direct effect theory posits that a lack of social support can negatively affect physiological health, with outcomes influenced by factors like personality, age, and gender (Duffin, 2024). The buffering effect theory, introduced by Cohen and Wills (1985), suggests that social support can protect individuals from the harmful effects of stressful life events, improving physiological well-being.

2.3.3.1 The direct effect of social support

Social support can directly mitigate stress by providing encouragement, feedback, and tangible assistance (Duffin, 2024). This effect shields individuals from stress's negative outcomes, such as receiving kind words or practical advice during difficult times (Cohen and Wills, 1985). It also promotes healthy behaviours like exercising, reducing fat intake, and quitting smoking, positively influencing health (Cohen, Gottlieb, and Underwood, 2000). Support from those practicing healthy habits can further reinforce these behaviours (Marmot and Wilkinson, 2006), enhancing both stress management and overall well-being.

2.3.3.2 The buffering effect of social support

The buffering effect suggests that social support can reduce the negative impact of stress by weakening the link between stress and poor health outcomes (Cohen and Wills, 1985). This effect enhances coping and alleviates physiological responses to stress (Barrera, 1986). Perceived support, such as informational, emotional, or

tangible aid, is more effective in buffering stress than mere social integration or enacted support (Marmot and Wilkinson, 2006; Barrera, 1986).

2.3.4 Types of social support

Understanding the various types of social support is essential for analysing how individuals seek and help. One foundational framework is the social support behavior code (SSBC) by Cutrona and Suhr (1992), as presented in Table 15, which categorises social support behaviors into five main types: informational support, tangible assistance, esteem support, network support, and emotional support.

Table 15: Social support behavior code (Cutrona and Suhr, 1992)

Type	Definition
Informational support 1- Advice/suggestion 2- Referral 3- Situation appraisal 4- Teaching	1- Gives insights and advises on what to do 2- Directs individual to another place for help 3- Offers reassurance or comfort in the situation 4- Gives information about the current situation or the necessary skills to handle it
Tangible assistance 5- Loan 6- Direct task 7- Indirect task 8- Active participation 9- Willingness	5- Offers to lend something, such as money 6- Assists with a task directly related to the recipient's stress 7- Proposes to handle one or more of the recipient's responsibilities during times of stress 8- Suggests joining the recipient in actions that help reduce stress 9- Offers willingness to help

Esteem Support 10-Compliments 11-Validation 12-Relief of blame	10-Expresses positive things about the person or highlight the recipient's capabilities 11-Acknowledges and confirms the recipient's viewpoint on the situation 12-Seeks to relieve the recipient from feelings of guilt related to the situation
Network support 13-Access 14-Presence 15-Companions	13-Provides a friendly offer to introduce the recipient to new companions or social connections 14-Provides a warm invitation to spend time together, assuring support and a comforting presence 15-Notifies the person about the presence of others who share similar interests or experiences and are available for support
Emotional support 16-Relationship 17-Physical Affection 18-Confidentiality 19-Sympathy 20-Listening 21-Empathy/understanding 22-Encouragement 23-Prayer	16-Highlights the importance of intimacy and love in the recipient's relationship 17-Gives physical contact such as hugs, kisses, holding hands, or patting on the shoulder 18-Commits to keep recipient's issues confidential 19-Expresses regret or sorrow for the recipient's condition 20-Provides considerate comments as the recipient speaks 21-Shows empathy by understanding or sharing a personal experience 22-Offers optimism and confidence for the future

As research expanded into online contexts, the original social support framework required adaptation to focus on seeking support, as it was originally centred on offering support (Lopes and Barbara, 2019). However, since this project examines support-seeking, offering support will not be discussed. Coursaris and Liu (2009) developed a modified version of the SSBC, as detailed in Table 16, specifically for online support settings and for types of seeking social support.

Table 16: Modified social support behavior code for support-seeking (Coursaris and Liu, 2009)

Type	Definition
Seeking informational support	Included specific questions for factual information, situation evaluation, or seeking advice.
Seeking emotional support	Show vulnerability and seek comfort.
Seeking esteem support	Seek validation or relief from blame.
Seeking network support	Request contact with those in a similar situation.
Seeking tangible support	Ask for financial, material, or one-on-one care.
Sharing personal experiences	Share thoughts, feelings, or personal stories.
Expression of gratitude	Express gratitude for previous support.
Congratulations	Acknowledge recipient's achievements with joy.

Coursaris and Liu (2009) adapted the SSBC framework for online support-seeking by including categories such as seeking informational support, emotional support, esteem support, network support, tangible support, sharing personal experiences, expressing gratitude, and congratulations. Algtewi, Owens, and Baker (2015) further refined this framework by adding seeking wellbeing information, expressions of care, and encouragement, making it more relevant to digital environments.

Despite the original framework's focus on offering support, these adaptations have proven useful in studying online support-seeking (Abusulttan, 2020; Da Moura Semedo, Bath, and Zhang, 2023; van Gastel *et al.*, 2023).

Although sharing personal experiences, expressing gratitude, congratulations, expressions of care, and encouragement are typically considered group interactions rather than direct types of support (Lopes and Barbara, 2019), these categories have been included as types of support sought in the current study. Group interactions were recognised as types of support in several studies (Armangau and Figeac, 2021; Petukhova *et al.*, 2020; Pham *et al.*, 2024; van Gastel *et al.*, 2023).

2.4 Rationale for the current research

Given the link between social support and DA, alongside the high prevalence and severe impacts of DA amongst adults globally—such as delaying or avoiding dental care, which can significantly affect daily activities (Aardal *et al.*, 2022)—the increasing use of OSGs may highlight the need to explore what users seek in these platforms (Coulson and Buchanan, 2022).

Studying DA specifically in OSGs is important because these platforms can provide a space where individuals can seek support without the barriers of stigma or face-to-face interaction, which is often critical for those with DA (Cohen, Fiske, and Newton, 2000).

Although social support can play a key role in managing DA, there is limited data on the specific types of social support sought in OSGs, particularly using a structured framework like the SSBC. This gap makes it difficult to understand the exact needs of individuals with DA when seeking support online.

Using the SSBC framework allowed for a structured analysis of support types in OSGs, offering insights into support needs and preferences. The current study analysed naturally occurring data from OSG posts, avoiding researcher influence, and ensured privacy by omitting personal details (Smedley and Coulson, 2018).

Content analysis, guided by the SSBC framework, categorised support types and assessed their frequency. This approach has been effectively used in various online health contexts, including DA (Abusulttan, 2020), eating disorders (Eichhorn, 2008), and other conditions (Algtewi, Owens, and Baker, 2015; Coursaris and Liu, 2009; van Gastel *et al.*, 2023).

The present study therefore built on previous studies by reporting the types and frequencies of social support sought by individuals with DA in OSGs. It extended the work of Buchanan and Coulson (2007), Coulson and Buchanan (2007), Buchanan, Coulson, and Malik (2010), and Abusulttan (2020) by providing updated data and findings on individuals' experiences of DA based on the SSBC framework.

More importantly, the practical implication of this study can lie in informing oral health professionals, OSG moderators, and platform designers about the specific support needs of individuals with DA, enabling more targeted interventions and improved OSG design to enhance user experience and support delivery, similar to how the ReConnect project in Norway by Gammon and colleagues (2017) addressed mental health care needs through tailored platform design and interventions.

2.5 Aim of the research

The aim was to assess the types and frequencies of social support sought within OSGs for individuals with DA.

2.6 Objectives of the research

- Search for existing OSGs for DA.
- Choose OSGs that exclusively deal with DA.
- Code and analyse the types of social support sought in the chosen OSGs, based on the modified SSBC framework by Algtewi, Owens, and Baker (2015).
- Report the types and frequencies of social support sought in the selected OSGs.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This chapter details the methodology for investigating social support types and frequencies in OSGs for DA. It describes the use of internet-mediated research, focusing on social support posts from Dental Fear Central. The chapter covers the selection criteria for OSGs and threads, data collection, and the use of qualitative and quantitative content analysis to interpret and quantify the data. It also addresses ethical considerations, outlines data analysis techniques, and explains the pilot study conducted to ensure accuracy and agreement between the researcher and supervisor.

3.2 Method

This study used internet-mediated research to analyse discussion forum posts, leveraging the advantages of non-interventional data collection (Smedley and Coulson, 2018; Verster *et al.*, 2019). However, it faced limitations such as the absence of non-verbal cues and potential issues with data representativeness (Germain *et al.*, 2017).

A combined deductive qualitative and quantitative content analysis approach was employed. This involved using predefined categories from existing literature (e.g., SSBC) and applying them to data (Kyngas and Kaakinen, 2019; Krippendorff, 2019). Qualitative content analysis interpreted and categorised text-based discussions, whilst quantitative content analysis assessed the frequency of themes (Coe and Scacco, 2017).

Content analysis supports statistical analysis by quantifying themes and patterns (Kleinheksel *et al.*, 2020; Gheyle and Jacobs, 2017). Reliability can be ensured through statistical tests like Cohen's Kappa (Zapf *et al.*, 2016; Cheung and Tai, 2021).

Content analysis is valued for its simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and ease of replication, but it has limitations, including potential subjectivity in coding and a focus on quantification over deeper contextual analysis (Erlingsson and Brysiewicz, 2017; Ninan, 2020).

3.2.1 Rationale for the method

This method was chosen because it can enable the study of discussion forum posts in their natural context, providing insights that might be missed in more controlled settings, such as interviews (Hallett and Barber, 2013). It avoids the biases associated with personal interactions and can capture data from diverse and geographically dispersed populations (Potter, 2002). Additionally, online research data is readily archived and accessible, overcoming the limitations of memory recall (Soos, Coulson, and Davies, 2022).

3.3 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

3.3.1 Online support groups selection

A search was conducted on Google using keywords related to OSGs and DA: *anxiety, bulletin boards, chat, community, dental, fear, forum, group, message boards, online, peer, support, and website.*

Groups were included based on the following inclusion criteria:

- Exclusively deal with DA.

Groups were excluded based on the following exclusion criteria:

- Non-English.
- Address health conditions other than DA.

- Require registration to access the threads within the group.
- Exclusively provide support from healthcare professionals or dentists, as identified through an examination of the terms and conditions as well as a review of threads within the group.

3.3.1.1 Rationale for groups selection

Inclusion and exclusion criteria for selecting OSGs were established to ensure relevance and feasibility. Groups were included if they focused solely on DA. Exclusion criteria included non-English groups, groups addressing conditions beyond DA, those requiring registration, and groups providing only professional support, to ensure the study centered on peer-to-peer support and was consistent with the English language requirement.

Following the application of the exclusion criteria, as shown in Fig. 1, only two OSGs—Dental Fear Central online forum and Facebook—exclusively dealt with DA.

Figure 1: Application of exclusion criteria for selecting online support groups

Facebook required registration, and the other six OSGs (Dentistry Forums, Health Boards, Mental Health Forum, Phobia Support Forum, Reddit, and Scope) focused on health issues unrelated to DA or offered only professional support. Consequently, Dental Fear Central was the only OSG that fully met the criteria. The list of the OSGs

identified, categorised by the location where their websites are based, can be seen in Table 17.

Table 17: List of online support groups categorised by location: United Kingdom, United States, and unspecified

Online support groups based in the United Kingdom	Online support groups based in the United States	Online support groups with unspecified location
Dental Fear Central	Facebook	Dentistry Forums
Mental Health Forum	Health Boards	
Phobia Support Forum	Reddit	
Scope		

Dental Fear Central is active since 2004, focuses on dental fear, anxiety, and phobia. At selection, it had 31,916 members, 30,431 threads, and 223,553 messages (Dental Fear Central, 2024). The site advises users during registration to avoid using real names and sharing private content, noting that such information is publicly accessible and can be found via search engines.

3.3.2 Threads selection

Threads were included based on the following inclusion criteria:

- Include the posting date.
- Seek at least one type of social support according to the modified version of the SSBC coding scheme by Algtewi, Owens, and Baker (2015).
- Are open to the public.

- Written in English.

Threads were excluded based on the following exclusion criteria:

- Threads unrelated to DA or the framework used.
- Threads written outside the study timeframe; even months of 2022, 2023, and February, April, and June for 2024.

3.3.2.1 Rationale for threads selection

Posts were selected based on relevance to DA and social support, with threads included if they addressed at least one type of social support according to the coding scheme. Only publicly available, English-language posts from 2022 to June 2024 were considered to ensure recent and accessible data. Threads were chosen from each even month of 2022 and 2023, plus February, April, and June of 2024, resulting in 375 posts (25 posts x 15 months), see Section 3.5.1 for justification.

Following the application of the exclusion criteria, as shown in Fig. 2, 271 threads were included in the research, which then coded and resulted in 531 statements.

Figure 2: Application of exclusion criteria for selecting support-seeking threads

3.4 Ethical considerations

Permission to use and publish data from the Dental Fear Central forum was granted by Sandra Morris (connect@dentalfearecentral.org) on December 18, 2023, following a request made on December 2, 2023. Details of this permission are available upon request.

In accordance with The British Psychological Society (2021) and Burles and Bally (2018), ethical considerations for content analysis of online forums were observed. Despite the forum being public, member privacy was protected by de-identifying data and using pseudonyms. No personal details, including ages, genders, and locations, were included in the study, and any names mentioned by members were replaced with "X". Quotes were paraphrased to further ensure confidentiality.

3.5 Data collection

Data for this study were collected from the Dental Fear Central forum, specifically from the 'Dental Phobia Support' main category, focusing on the 'Support' subcategory. This subforum was chosen because it is dedicated to threads where individuals seek help and support, making it ideal for capturing support-seeking behaviours relevant to the research objectives.

The criteria to select threads was based on a predetermined number of threads (Smedley and Coulson, 2018). Twenty-five threads were randomly selected from each even month of 2022, 2023, and 2024, including February, April, June, August, October, and December. However, for 2024, only February, April, and June were selected due to the timing at that point. This process was conducted using an electronic random number generator to ensure fairness (Smedley and Coulson, 2018).

3.5.1 Rationale for selecting 25 threads per even month of 2022, 2023, and 2024

Selecting a fixed number of threads over a specific time period ensured manageable data and minimised subjective judgment (Smedley and Coulson, 2018). Sampling methods in OSG content analysis vary: Abusulttan (2020) and Algtewi, Owens, and Baker (2015) used random sampling, whilst van Gastel *et al.* (2023), Petukhova *et al.* (2020), and Winzelberg (1997) analysed posts from defined date ranges or periods. Armangau and Figeac (2021) and Eichhorn (2008) selected threads based on specific criteria, and Coulson (2005) reviewed all posts over an 8-month period, with other

studies extending their analysis over several years (Coulson *et al.*, 2007; Mo and Coulson, 2008; Coulson and Greenwood, 2012).

3.6 Data analysis

Data analysis was conducted utilising deductive qualitative and quantitative content analysis based on the modified SSBC by Algtewi, Owens, and Baker (2015).

3.6.1 Rationale for choosing content analysis over other methodological approaches

Content analysis was chosen to explore the types and frequencies of social support sought for DA within OSGs. This method quantifies threads into numbers and percentages (Gheyle and Jacobs, 2017; Krippendorff, 2019), enabling comparison between different types of support. Thematic analysis, though valuable for interpreting patterns and themes in qualitative data (Smedley and Coulson, 2018), was not used as it focuses on depth and meaning rather than quantification (Humble and Mozelius, 2022).

3.7 Coding

A modified SSBC was used as the primary coding system for content analysis of threads in this study. Threads were reviewed and coded multiple times, with all text highlighted, even if it did not fit specific categories. Multiple codes were assigned to statements reflecting various types of social support sought. See Table 18 for the modified SSBC coding system used.

Table 18: Modified social support behavior code for support-seeking (Algtewi, Owens, and Baker, 2015)

Type	Definition
Seeking informational support	Included specific questions for information, situation evaluation, or seeking advice.
Seeking wellbeing information	Ask about supporting others.
Seeking emotional support	Show vulnerability or psychological weakness and seek comfort.
Seeking esteem support	Seek validation or relief from blame.
Seeking network support	Request contact with those in a similar situation.
Seeking tangible support	Ask for financial, material, or one-on-one care.
Sharing personal experiences	Share thoughts, feelings, or personal stories.
Expression of gratitude	Express gratitude for previous support.
Congratulations	Acknowledge recipient's achievements with joy.
Expression of care	Convey concern for others.
Encouragement	Send messages of hope and confidence.

3.7.1 Rationale for choosing the modified version of the social support behavior code

The modified SSBC by Algtewi, Owens, and Baker (2015) was chosen to enhance understanding of support types in OSGs. It builds on the original SSBC by Cutrona and Suhr (1992), which categorised support into five types: informational, emotional, esteem, network, and tangible. It also incorporates additions from Coursaris and Liu (2009), such as sharing personal experiences, gratitude, and congratulations, and further refines the framework with categories for seeking well-being information, expressions of care, and encouragement

3.8 Pilot study

A pilot study involving 10 randomly selected posts from the Dental Fear Central forum was conducted by the primary researcher and supervisor. Cohen's Kappa was 0.61 to 0.80, indicating substantial agreement (Gheyle and Jacobs, 2017). Partial disagreement occurred in distinguishing between seeking emotional support and sharing personal experiences, attributed to differences in language fluency. Statements with phrases like "hello" and "thank you" were recoded based on their context.

Chapter 4: Results

This chapter outlines the results of the content analysis, highlighting the types and frequencies of social support that were sought. A summary of the key findings is provided at the end of this chapter.

4.1 Types and frequencies of social support sought

A total of 271 threads, resulting in 531 statements, were analysed from each even month in 2022 and 2023, as well as from February, April, and June in 2024, based on the modified version of the SSBC for seeking social support by Algtewi, Owens, and Baker (2015). Some threads sought only one type of social support, whilst others sought more than one type. Most posts sought two types of social support (58.7%). No posts sought more than four types. Table 19 summarises the distribution of social support types sought per thread in the 271 threads.

Table 19: Distribution of social support types sought per thread in the 271 threads

Number of types	Number of threads	Percentage
Threads sought one type of social support	75	27.7
Threads sought two types of social support	159	58.7
Threads sought three types of social support	34	12.5
Threads sought four types of social support	3	1.1
Threads sought more than four types of social support	0	0.0
Total	271	100

Of the 531 statements, the most frequently sought type of support was sharing personal experiences (53.4%), followed by seeking informational support (31.1%), and then seeking emotional support (9.8%). There were no statements coded under seeking esteem support, seeking tangible support, or congratulations. Table 20 shows the types and frequencies of social support sought across all 271 threads.

Table 20: Types and frequencies of social support sought across all 271 threads

Sought support	Number of statements	Percentage
Seeking informational support	165	31.1
Seeking wellbeing information	1	0.2
Seeking emotional support	52	9.8
Seeking esteem support	0	0.0
Seeking network support	2	0.4
Seeking tangible support	0	0.0
Sharing personal experiences	284	53.4
Expression of gratitude	3	0.6
Congratulations	0	0.0
Expression of care	8	1.5
Encouragement	16	3.0
Total	531	100

In the following sections, more detailed textual descriptions are provided for each of the 11 types of social support sought.

4.1.1 Seeking informational support

Statements coded under this section comprised specific questions related to DA aimed at obtaining factual information, seeking advice or suggestions, or helping to evaluate a particular situation. The majority of messages were related to procedure-related inquiries, individual-related questions, and provider-related concerns.

Procedure-related inquiries were the most frequent and mainly concerned how individuals manage their fear of specific dental procedures. For instance, many members expressed anxiety about injections. One person posted:

"Is anyone else terrified of anesthesia and its effects? How do you manage to relax? I'm extremely anxious and wondering if they numb the roof of your mouth for an upper tooth procedure—does anyone have any information?"

Another example involved fear of drills and gag-inducing procedures. One member shared:

"I've been experiencing jaw and toothache pain. I'm anxious about the sound of the drill and struggle with a gag reflex during procedures. What are some effective ways to calm my nerves? I'm feeling extremely overwhelmed."

Questions about gum grafts were also common. A member posted:

"For those who have undergone a gum graft, how was your experience? I've heard that the recovery can be more challenging than the surgery itself, and I'm feeling extremely anxious about both aspects."

Concerns about enduring root canal treatment were another topic. One individual asked:

"Has anyone used a sedative for dental anxiety, and did it help enough to get through a root canal? The procedure will last between 1.5 and 2 hours, and I'm concerned about being able to manage without swallowing during that time."

Members also sought advice on handling the discomfort of getting a filling. A participant posted:

"Does anyone have any tips for managing the experience of getting a filling? My biggest concern is the feeling of having something in my mouth and the difficulty of breathing and swallowing."

Another member asked about what to expect during a scaling and root planning procedure:

"I have a deep cleaning appointment with injections scheduled for tomorrow morning at 10am, and I'm worried about the pain. Could someone please provide advice on what to expect during the procedure and how painful it might be?"

Individual-related questions often focused on pain management. For example, one member asked:

"This tooth frequently causes infections and abscesses, leading to intense pain. My anxiety has been so severe that I couldn't visit the dentist for sedation. Now, I'm struggling to sleep due to the pain— is this normal, and should I continue waiting for my medication to take effect?"

Another instance involved pain and sensitivity after a filling. A person posted:

"I went for a filling refill, but they couldn't numb me completely, and I experienced sharp pain from the drilling, possibly due to my high anxiety. They stopped the procedure, placed a temporary filling, and rescheduled for when I could use nitrous sedation and take an anxiety medication. I'm also experiencing increased sensitivity to cold foods. Is this normal after a filling?"

Provider-related concerns were less frequent and focused on issues with dentist behaviour. For example, users asked how to deal with poor manners. One person posted:

"I have a strong fear of dentists and their staff acting in ways that are pushy, aggressive, deceptive, angry, raise their voices, use high-pressure tactics, or are only focused on making money. This fear makes it very difficult for me to communicate with them, ask questions, or negotiate. I would really appreciate any stories, tips, or advice."

4.1.2 Seeking wellbeing information

Messages in this section were about supporting others (only one statement was identified that fits this type). For example, a member was seeking advice on how to encourage their father, who had neglected dental care despite significant issues, to seek treatment for their worsening teeth and gums, asked:

"I'm posting this mainly out of concern for my father. I'm unsure if he's afraid or simply doesn't think it's necessary, but he definitely needs to visit the dentist and address his dental issues. What should I do now? I want him to get treated and stay healthy."

4.1.3 Seeking emotional support

In this type of social support, statements showed vulnerability or psychological weakness and sought comfort. The majority of messages were related to personal struggles in daily life and seeking encouragement for visiting the dentist.

Most posts addressed how dental issues were affecting overall well-being. For example, one member shared:

"Mainly my goal is to be happy and healthy, and my teeth and mouth are really bringing me down in every aspect of my life. I'd appreciate any support or words of encouragement with this from anyone."

Another member, who experienced DA impacting their daily life, posted:

"Does anyone know where people can have therapy to talk about their dental problems and phobias of dentists and talk about other things that they are worried about? It is taking over my life and I am in tears every day and I really need to talk to someone."

Encouragement to visit the dentist was frequently sought. One user posted:

"I'm unsure how to proceed as I need treatment urgently but am in severe pain. I experience panic attacks and even faint at the dentist. What should I do? It's a terrible situation, and I find myself dreading both the dentist and my life."

Another instance of seeking encouragement involved an individual preparing for their first dental appointment in 15 years. They posted:

"Just looking for support, I have my first dentist appointment in 15 years coming up. I have already told the dentist I'm scared. I have a real phobia of the dentist due to past dental trauma. I'm terrified and extremely anxious."

4.1.4 Seeking esteem support

This type of social support was intended to cover messages in which members sought validation or relief from blame; however, no statements could be coded under this category.

4.1.5 Seeking network support

Statements that requested contact with those in a similar situation were coded under this category (only two statements were coded under this type). For example, a contributor expressed hope that the group could connect them with others who have faced similar challenges:

"It's a bit of a long shot, but I thought if anyone has experienced a similar issue, this would be the place to find them."

In another example, an individual who was anxious about the possibility of needing a tooth extraction reached out to connect with others and wrote:

"I'm really scared to make the call and hear that I need a tooth pulled. I'm not sure what to do and would really like to talk to someone."

4.1.6 Seeking tangible support

This category involved statements that asked for financial, material, or one-on-one care; however, no messages could be coded under this type of social support.

4.1.7 Sharing personal experiences

Messages under this category shared thoughts, feelings, or personal stories. The majority were related to panic attacks due to procedures, anxiety from visiting the dentist, pain in daily life, and interactions with the staff.

Most messages focused on panic attack stories. For instance, one member who experienced panic over fillings posted:

"I need three fillings, and apparently, they have to be silver. The dentist offered to do them immediately, so I signed the forms, got ready, and sat down. However, I had a severe panic attack, fainted three times, and needed oxygen for about 15 minutes."

Another example of panic involved someone's fear of injections:

"I went for a routine check-up, and the dentist, looking troubled, informed me I had cavities in two back molars that needed fillings and numbing. As someone with a lifelong fear of needles, I panicked, jumped out of the chair, and frantically cried "No! No! No!" while looking at the nurse, the dentist, and my mum."

A further example included a member who panicked over the sensation of getting numb:

"I'm not afraid of the needle or the drill itself, but I fear the sensation of the injection. It makes me feel like I can't breathe and that my throat might close up. This fear causes me to panic, cry, and feel like I'm making a complete fool of myself."

Anxiety from going to the dentist frequently affected individuals. For example, one person mentioned how their appointment was disrupting their sleep and causing nightmares:

"I know I can't cancel, and I have to go through with it because the waiting, wondering, and letting my thoughts spiral about what might be wrong—and imagining all the different scenarios—is worse than just going and finding out. I just wish I could manage my anxiety better, but it's my past trauma coming through. I've been having several nightmares over the past few nights, and I know I'll have more tonight and won't sleep well."

Another instance showed how rising anxiety about an upcoming dental appointment was impacting mental health:

"I have my first dental appointment in about 16 years tomorrow, and I can feel my anxiety increasing with every minute. I'm scared to go, but I'm also scared to cancel, if that makes sense, because I know I can't keep living with my teeth in this condition. It's starting to take too much of a toll on my mental health."

A more example involved anxiety caused by previous dental trauma:

"I'm afraid I'll have another panic attack, similar to what happened during my second filling. On one hand, I think completing this check-up would be a significant achievement for me, but on the other hand, I'm unsure if I can manage it tomorrow. I feel like a coward."

Pain in daily life was also a frequent topic. For instance, one person described how intense pain was affecting their eating:

"The pain is now so intense that I experience daily headaches. It's impacting my eating, and I'm constantly worried about my teeth being unhealthy. My fear of visiting the dentist remains so overwhelming that I can barely consider the idea."

Another individual highlighted how their condition was affecting their job:

"I can't endure the embarrassment, pain, and cost, and I'm worried about how I'll eat or speak, especially in public. My job requires me to stand and talk to others, and I fear I won't be able to manage it."

Interactions with the staff were less frequent. One individual shared their feelings of being blamed by the dentist:

"Most of my resentment is directed at the dentist, who made me feel as though I was to blame for everything going wrong. I believe he should have anticipated the possibility of the outcome, even though it was a rare side effect."

4.1.8 Expression of gratitude

This aspect of social support included messages that express gratitude for previous support. One example is when a member expressed gratitude for the support received from the community:

"Thank you for helping me express my anxiety. I'm glad to say that it's now at a healthy level."

An additional example is when a user recognised the positive impact of the forum and the support provided by others:

“Thank you to everyone who has contributed to this website. The shared stories and supportive atmosphere have helped me reach this point!”

Another instance is when an individual acknowledged the support received from the forum and shared their appreciation for the shared experiences and advice:

“I wanted to share on this forum because reading about others' experiences has been really helpful to me in the past, giving me an idea of what to expect. So, thank you to everyone who has ever posted!”

4.1.9 Congratulations

This type was meant to include messages acknowledging recipients' achievements with joy; however, no statements were coded under this category.

4.1.10 Expression of care

Statements within this section focused on conveying concern for others. A specific example is when a user expressed concern for others whilst sharing their own struggles with anxiety:

“The anxiety is consuming all my thoughts, and I just needed to express it instead of keeping it bottled up. I apologize to anyone else going through this.”

One more illustration involved an individual expressing their intention to offer comfort to others facing similar challenges:

“I'm sharing this in hopes of providing comfort to others facing similar challenges. I'm not a dentist, just an ordinary person sharing my experience.”

A further instance involved a contributor who cautioned others about reading their thread if they were anxious about an upcoming filling:

“If you're anxious about an upcoming filling, you might want to skip this.”

4.1.11 Encouragement

This category included messages that express hope and confidence. A relevant example is when a member encouraged themselves by recalling a past positive experience with nitrous oxide:

“I'm hoping everything will be fine, and I keep reminding myself how relaxed I was about needles while on nitrous. I even opened my mouth willingly with no hesitation! I know I can do it again!”

Another example is demonstrated by a user who, despite feeling nervous about their upcoming procedure to fill multiple cavities, found comfort in reminding their previous experience with a similar treatment:

“Tomorrow I have three cavities to get filled, which makes me nervous. However, I remind myself that I've had this done before about nine years ago, so I know I can handle it.”

A different illustration is when an individual expressed their belief in personal strength and control over health decisions:

"I believe we are stronger than we realize and have full control over our decisions and treatments. Ultimately, good health is invaluable."

4.2 Summary of key findings

The study identified 8 OSGs for DA, with only one fully meeting the inclusion criteria, Dental Fear Central forum. Analysis of the 271 threads from this online forum, containing 531 statements, revealed that most threads sought two types of social support. The most frequently sought types of social support within these posts were sharing personal experiences, seeking informational support, and seeking emotional support. No statements were coded under seeking esteem support, tangible support, or congratulations.

Personal experiences shared often involved feelings of panic attacks due to procedures, anxiety from visiting the dentist, pain in daily life, and interactions with the staff. Members commonly sought advice on dental procedures, pain management, and communications with dentists. Users also sought emotional support for dealing with personal struggles and encouragement for visiting the dentist. Expressions of gratitude, care, and encouragement were present, though less frequent compared to other types of support.

Chapter 5: Discussion

The present study aimed to explore the types and frequencies of social support sought within OSGs for individuals with DA through content analysis of threads posted in these groups. In the discussion below, the following will be discussed: the availability of OSGs for individuals with DA, the types and frequencies of social support sought within these groups, as well as the study's limitations and strengths.

5.1 What online support groups are available for individuals with dental anxiety?

The current study identified eight OSGs that may be relevant for individuals with DA. Despite this, only two platforms—Dental Fear Central discussion forum and Facebook—met the criteria for being specifically dedicated to DA. However, the latter was excluded due to the registration requirement to access threads, leaving Dental Fear Central as the only platform meeting all the criteria. This finding aligns with other studies on OSGs for DA, which also selected only the Dental Fear Central forum as their primary OSG (Abusulttan, 2020; Buchanan and Coulson, 2007; Buchanan, Coulson, and Malik, 2010; Coulson and Buchanan, 2007).

5.2 What types and frequencies of social support are sought in online support groups for dental anxiety?

The content analysis of 271 threads from the Dental Fear Central online forum revealed that the majority of threads sought two types of social support (58.7%), followed by those seeking one type (27.7%), and three types (12.5%). Threads seeking four types of support were quite rare (1.1%), and no threads sought more than four types of social support (0.0%).

This distribution is consistent with the research on head and neck cancer (Algtewi, Owens, and Baker, 2015), which also showed a predominance of threads seeking two types of social support. However, in that study, the number of threads seeking one

type of support was equal to those seeking three types, whereas the current project found a greater disparity between these categories. Unlike this, many studies on OSGs did not investigate the number of types of social support sought per thread (Abusulttan, 2020; Armangau and Figeac, 2021; Coursaris and Liu, 2009; Eichhorn, 2008; Petukhova *et al.*, 2020; Pham *et al.*, 2024; van Gastel *et al.*, 2023; Winzelberg, 1997).

This analysis of threads, which resulted in 531 statements, showed that individuals used the group to seek various types of support, particularly for sharing personal experiences and seeking informational support.

The most frequently sought type of social support amongst the 531 statements was sharing personal experiences (53.4%); this might be due to the anonymity and control provided by the online platform, which may reduce the fear of embarrassment or judgment compared to traditional face-to-face groups, encouraging individuals to seek support through self-disclosure (Wright *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, the sense of community within the group may further motivate individuals to share their experiences, as they feel part of a larger community that understands their fears (Liu *et al.*, 2019).

For example, Buchanan, Coulson, and Malik (2010) found that "*talking to a computer is much easier*" and "*this big dark secret I can't share with anyone*" were two common threads in their study. These authors found that the internet support group functioned as a valuable environment for disclosing fears and discussing anxieties. The challenge many members face in sharing their DA with those around them may reflect a common sentiment of feeling misunderstood or dismissed by their immediate social circles (Abusulttan, 2020). This experience may highlight why individuals turn to online groups where they can discuss their fears openly without the risk of negative reactions.

The predominance of sharing personal experiences in this study supports the buffering effect theory of perceived social support (Cohen and Wills, 1985), which suggests that the belief that support will be available can encourage individuals to disclose their experiences, reinforcing the protective buffer against stressors and enhancing coping abilities. In the present study, it could be that the high frequency of sharing personal experiences indicates that individuals find reassurance in the belief that support is available, which may help them manage their DA more effectively.

Additionally, it aligns with social comparison theory (Festinger, 1954), which posits that individuals seek to evaluate themselves by comparing with others. In the present study, it could be that sharing personal experiences allows individuals with DA to engage in comparisons, which may impact their self-evaluation based on the experiences and outcomes of others in the group.

Furthermore, it supports the empowerment theory (Zimmerman, 1995), which indicates that active participation in OSGs can enhance confidence, social well-being, and a sense of control through empowering processes such as sharing experiences (Liu and Wang, 2021). In the current study, it could be that individuals with DA who share their personal experiences experience increased confidence and social well-being, as well as a greater sense of control over their condition (Vainauskiene and Vaitkiene, 2021).

Moreover, it corresponds with the affordance theory (Gibson, 1986), which highlights self-presentation and narration as key elements (Coulson, Bullock, and Rodham, 2017), allowing individuals to share and discuss personal experiences whilst understanding others' experiences. In the present study, it could be that sharing personal experiences helps individuals with DA reduce feelings of isolation through these therapeutic affordances (Dodemaide *et al.*, 2021).

The second most frequently sought type of social support was seeking informational support (31.1%), which may suggest a strong desire amongst contributors to acquire

knowledge about DA management strategies, treatment options, and coping mechanisms. This type of support might serve as a key role in empowering individuals to make informed decisions about their dental care and understand their condition better (Buchanan and Coulson, 2007; Buchanan, Coulson, and Malik, 2010).

This aligns with the optimal matching theory (Cutrona and Russell, 1990), which suggests that informational support is most effective when it addresses specific characteristics of the stressor. In particular, informational support tends to be most beneficial when individuals are dealing with stressors that are perceived as controllable, such as managing specific aspects of a dental procedure or addressing individual-related concerns. In the current study, it could be that the desire for informational support reflects an optimal match, where individuals with DA seek information about procedures, such as managing fear of injections, drills, and fillings; pain management, such as coping with sensitivity after a filling; and interactions with dental providers, such as handling dentist behaviour. This support may be believed to help them manage their anxiety and make informed decisions about their dental care.

Additionally, it aligns with the uses and gratifications model (Falgoust *et al.*, 2022), which suggests that users turn to OSGs for their interactive, demassified, and asynchronous features to satisfy specific informational needs. In the present study, it could be that preference for seeking informational support reflects how individuals with DA use these platforms to obtain tailored information that addresses their unique concerns.

In addition, it fits with the direct effect theory of social support (Cohen and Wills, 1985). Acquiring knowledge can directly enhance individuals' health by promoting healthy behaviours and thus, may increase their sense of control over their DA. This is in line with many studies examining OSGs in relation to other health conditions, involving diabetes (Pham *et al.*, 2024), women with Essure-related complaints (van Gastel *et al.*, 2023), transgender issues (Armangau and Figeac, 2021), skin cancer (Petukhova *et al.*, 2020), head and neck cancer (Algtewi, Owens, and Baker, 2015),

HIV/AIDS (Coursaris and Liu, 2009), and eating disorders (Eichhorn, 2008; Winzelberg, 1997). This may suggest that sharing personal experiences and seeking informational support are the main functions of OSGs for health issues.

Within these previous studies, sharing personal experiences often outweighs informational support in some cases (Algtewi, Owens, and Baker, 2015; Eichhorn, 2008; Petukhova *et al.*, 2020; van Gastel *et al.*, 2023; Winzelberg, 1997), whilst other research has found the opposite (Armangau and Figeac, 2021; Coursaris and Liu, 2009; Pham *et al.*, 2024). In Abusulttan's (2020) study on DA, sharing personal experiences was not assessed due to the framework used, which did not include this category of social support. However, informational support was assessed and was the second most frequent type, which aligns with the results of the current project.

The third most frequent type of support sought was seeking emotional support (9.8%), which may be due to the forum's supportive environment where individuals feel safe to express their psychological weaknesses or vulnerabilities. This finding aligns with studies on women with Essure-related complaints (van Gastel *et al.*, 2023), transgender issues (Armangau and Figeac, 2021), head and neck cancer (Algtewi, Owens, and Baker, 2015), and HIV/AIDS (Coursaris and Liu, 2009), where seeking emotional support was also prevalent, though not the most frequent type.

However, it was reported as the most frequent type in the DA study by Abusulttan (2020). This type of support was reflected less frequently in findings on diabetes (Pham *et al.*, 2024) and eating disorders (Winzelberg, 1997). It was not registered in few papers (Eichhorn, 2008; Petukhova *et al.*, 2020). These differences could be attributed to the nature of the conditions studied and the varying needs of the individuals seeking support.

The types of support presented, although relatively infrequent compared to sharing personal experiences, seeking informational support, and seeking emotional support,

include seeking wellbeing information (0.2%), seeking network support (0.4%), expression of gratitude (0.6%), expression of care (1.5%), and encouragement (3.0%).

The low frequency of seeking well-being information, which involved asking about how to support others (e.g., family members), might be due to the specific focus of the online bulletin board. This group may emphasise personal support rather than general guidance on supporting others. This trend was observed in the article of head and neck cancer by Algtewi, Owens, and Baker (2015), where this type of support was found at low frequency. However, other studies did not assess this form of support, as their frameworks for coding threads did not comprise this type of social support (Abusulttan, 2020; Armangau and Figeac, 2021; Coursaris and Liu, 2009; Eichhorn, 2008; Petukhova *et al.*, 2020; Pham *et al.*, 2024; van Gastel *et al.*, 2023; Winzelberg, 1997).

The relatively low frequency of seeking network support could be attributed to the nature of the online group, where members might prefer building connections through other social platforms rather than a specialised support forum. This finding is consistent with the complete absence of network support in the analysis of head and neck cancer by Algtewi, Owens, and Baker (2015). On the other hand, seeking network support was found at high frequency in the research on transgender issues by Armangau and Figeac (2021). Other studies did not capture this type of support due to the limitations of their coding frameworks, which did not encompass this category of social support (Abusulttan, 2020; Coursaris and Liu, 2009; Eichhorn, 2008; Petukhova *et al.*, 2020; Pham *et al.*, 2024; van Gastel *et al.*, 2023; Winzelberg, 1997).

The infrequency of expression of gratitude might result from the members' focus on seeking direct support rather than acknowledging contributions. On the contrary, expressions of gratitude were found at high frequency in findings on women with Essure-related complaints (van Gastel *et al.*, 2023), head and neck cancer (Algtewi, Owens, and Baker, 2015), and HIV/AIDS (Coursaris and Liu, 2009). This type of support was not included in the frameworks of coding threads used in various studies

(Abusulttan, 2020; Armangau and Figeac, 2021; Eichhorn, 2008; Petukhova *et al.*, 2020; Pham *et al.*, 2024; Winzelberg, 1997).

Similarly, the lower frequency of expression of care could be related to the forum's focus on shared experiences and practical advice rather than emotional expressions, which may be less highlighted in online interactions due to anonymity. This finding is consistent with the study of head and neck cancer by Algtewi, Owens, and Baker (2015). Expressions of care were not captured in several studies due to the frameworks they used (Abusulttan, 2020; Armangau and Figeac, 2021; Coursaris and Liu, 2009; Eichhorn, 2008; Petukhova *et al.*, 2020; Pham *et al.*, 2024; van Gastel *et al.*, 2023; Winzelberg, 1997).

Encouragement might be less frequent because members may prioritise specific forms of support such as experiential and informational rather than motivational. This result aligns with results from studies on women with Essure-related complaints (van Gastel *et al.*, 2023), eating disorders (Eichhorn, 2008), and head and neck cancer (Algtewi, Owens, and Baker, 2015). In opposition, encouragement was found at higher frequency in studies on DA (Abusulttan, 2020) and HIV/AIDS (Coursaris and Liu, 2009). This type of support was not accounted for in various articles as their frameworks did not encompass this category of social support (Armangau and Figeac, 2021; Petukhova *et al.*, 2020; Pham *et al.*, 2024; Winzelberg, 1997).

The least frequent types of support in the present data were seeking esteem support (0.0%), seeking tangible support (0.0%), and congratulations (0.0%).

The total lack of seeking esteem support could be due to the forum's nature, where the focus is more on sharing own experiences and seeking advice rather than boosting self-esteem. This result contrasts with the study on DA (Abusulttan, 2020), where esteem support was found at a higher frequency. It also contrasts with the studies on Essure-related complaints (van Gastel *et al.*, 2023), head and neck cancer (Algtewi, Owens, and Baker, 2015), and HIV/AIDS (Coursaris and Liu, 2009), where it was

observed at a lower frequency. This form of support was not covered in some research due to the omission of this type in their analysis frameworks (Armangau and Figeac, 2021; Eichhorn, 2008; Petukhova *et al.*, 2020; Pham *et al.*, 2024; Winzelberg, 1997).

The complete absence of tangible support could also be due to the group's nature, where asking for material assistance online might be rare. This absence aligns with findings from the studies on Essure-related complaints (van Gastel *et al.*, 2023) and DA (Abusulttan, 2020). However, it was found to be of low frequency in studies on head and neck cancer (Algtewi, Owens, and Baker, 2015) and HIV/AIDS (Coursaris and Liu, 2009). Seeking tangible support was not mentioned in several papers due to the fact that their frameworks did not include this type of support (Armangau and Figeac, 2021; Eichhorn, 2008; Petukhova *et al.*, 2020; Pham *et al.*, 2024; Winzelberg, 1997).

Lastly, the lack of congratulations may be a result of the forum's focus on addressing DA, where members are primarily concerned with finding solutions and support rather than celebrating achievements. This absence was also observed in the research on Essure-related complaints (van Gastel *et al.*, 2023) and head and neck cancer (Algtewi, Owens, and Baker, 2015), but was found at a low frequency in the HIV/AIDS research (Coursaris and Liu, 2009). This type of support was not documented in various studies as their coding frameworks did not contain this category (Abusulttan, 2020; Armangau and Figeac, 2021; Eichhorn, 2008; Petukhova *et al.*, 2020; Pham *et al.*, 2024; Winzelberg, 1997).

5.3 Study limitations

There were a number of limitations in the study that are detailed below.

Firstly, the sample size of 271 threads may not be representative of the broader population of individuals with DA, potentially limiting the generalisability of the findings. Obtaining representative samples through the internet has been seen as

particularly problematic, mainly due to the absence of a central database of all internet users (Latkovikj and Popovska, 2020) and the exclusion of individuals who do not have internet access, such as those from low-income settings (Smith, Bulbul, and Jones, 2017).

Due to the unobtrusive nature of this online research, which did not involve direct contact with individuals, several sociodemographic details were not recorded. The genders of users who wrote the posts were not recorded, which may have affected the comprehensiveness of demographic analysis. This limitation is important because gender can affect both the understanding and dissemination of information amongst males and females (Tannenbaum, Greaves, and Graham, 2016). In addition, the ages of members were not documented, which may have impacted the understanding of demographic trends (Diaz *et al.*, 2021). The locations of contributors were also not recorded, limiting insights into geographical variations in support-seeking behaviors (Shevchenko and Reips, 2023). Furthermore, socioeconomic status such as education, income, and occupation were not described. Including these sociodemographic factors could have enabled the reader to better understand the context in which these data were generated (Antonoplis, 2022).

Additionally, the measures used to analyse the data were content analysis, which may have introduced bias or subjectivity into the interpretation of the results due to the inherent limitations of this method (Liau, 2022). The deductive approach employed in this analysis also had its limitations. It may overlook important content and limit the depth of analysis by focusing solely on predetermined categories (Kleinheksel *et al.*, 2020).

The framework was based on Cutrona and Suhr's (1992) SSBC framework of offline social support, which was later modified by Coursaris and Liu (2009) for online social support and further adapted by Algtewi, Owens, and Baker (2015). This modified framework lacked appropriate categories for some statements. For example, a statement like *'I know I've done this to myself and I'm not looking for sympathy'* might

reflect self-blame, but no category was available to capture this nuance. Similarly, common phrases such as 'hello,' 'good morning,' and 'thank you' did not fit into any existing category for greetings and courtesies. Moreover, using a set of predefined categories based on previous theories might raise the risk of overlap between the data and the categories' definitions, which could add to bias or subjectivity in the interpretation (Rimmel and Cordazzo, 2021).

The restricted inclusion criteria, including the exclusion of private groups (e.g., Facebook-based groups) and non-English language groups/threads, may have limited the scope of the study and excluded diverse perspectives on DA. The data collection method of selecting 25 posts per even month might have introduced sampling bias and missed significant discussions outside the selected timeframe. High volumes of daily activity on forums can lead to an overwhelming number of messages, making it challenging for researchers to analyse every post (Smedley and Coulson, 2018).

Finally, the researcher's background may have influenced the interpretation of the data, introducing potential biases, particularly in understanding culturally specific expressions of DA. Data interpretation was subjective, and the researcher's personal experiences, beliefs, and assumptions may have influenced their analysis and understanding of the findings (Olmos-Vega *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, the researcher's fluency in the language used in the study may have affected the accuracy of data analysis. Limited language proficiency could also hinder the effective communication of knowledge, which may impede the reader's understanding of the issues presented (Balan, 2021).

5.4 Study strengths

Several strengths of the study are outlined below.

Firstly, the research was guided by theory throughout all stages, from planning to the interpretation of results. During the planning phases, the theoretical framework

informed the research design and clarified the study's objectives. In the analysis phase, it ensured that the research remained accountable to the data, whilst theory-driven interpretation highlighted the applicability of the theoretical framework. This approach contributed to the accumulation of knowledge by connecting the study to prior research in the field of OSGs (Haardorfer, 2019; Pigott, 2017).

Additionally, the study's comprehensive analysis of 271 threads and 531 statements provided a rich understanding of social support in OSGs for DA. As one of the first studies to systematically categorise social support types in these groups, it addressed a gap in the literature. By comparing findings with research on OSGs for other health conditions, the study situated its results within a broader context of online support research.

Furthermore, the study's methodological strengths included its use of naturally occurring data. Collecting retrospective data from online sources minimised researcher bias, as the data were produced independently of the research agenda (Germain *et al.*, 2017). This method allowed participants to reflect and validate their own data, leading to more authentic and honest discussions of sensitive issues (Ninan, 2020). The unobtrusive nature of the data collection method maintained ethical considerations by minimising disruption to the online community, thereby supporting the study's integrity and respect for its members (Smedley and Coulson, 2018).

Finally, the study's interdisciplinary approach, which bridged dentistry, psychology, and online communication, along with its practical relevance for OSG design and oral health professionals, underscored its significant contribution to understanding how individuals coped with health-related anxieties in the digital age (Griffiths, 2017). Moreover, this research was amongst the first to link theories of online communities and social support within the context of DA.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

OSGs appear to be valuable sources of social support for individuals experiencing DA, offering a platform where users can seek peer assistance. The inherent features of online platforms, such as interactivity, demassification, and asynchronicity, may encourage more sharing and provide a sense of control over DA (Naslund *et al.*, 2020).

Participation in OSGs for DA may lead users to feel more informed and optimistic about their health conditions, thus promoting a stronger sense of self-efficacy (Vainauskiene and Vaitkiene, 2021). Additionally, group interactions, such as sharing experiences about DA, might reduce feelings of isolation when users both share and read about others' experiences (Dodemaide *et al.*, 2021).

Moreover, the anonymity provided by OSGs may help reduce stigma and enhance participation, allowing users to engage without fear of judgment from others (Pan *et al.*, 2020). This is particularly important for those who have experienced misunderstandings and feelings of guilt from close family members who might not fully grasp their fears (Abusulttan, 2020).

6.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made for future research and future practice/policy development to enhance support for individuals with DA.

6.2.1 Future research

- Future research could adopt a longitudinal observational study design to explore the long-term impact of using OSGs for DA on health and well-being. Researchers might recruit adults, aged 18 or older, who have been active on Dental Fear Central for at least six months. Simple random sampling could be employed to help achieve representative participation (Rudolph *et al.*, 2023). Informed consent would be obtained from both selected participants and group moderators (The British Psychological Society, 2021). Participants would then complete an online questionnaire through Google Forms, such as the oral health impact profile-14 (OHIP-14), which measures aspects like oral function, orofacial pain, appearance, and psychosocial impact (John *et al.*, 2022). Three questionnaires would be delivered over an 18-month period: a follow-up survey after six months, and a third survey six months later. A similar study was conducted for OSGs concerning depression and reported by Bessiere *et al.* (2010).
- Future research could utilise a cross-sectional study design to assess the perceived impacts of OSGs for DA on users' experiences and their overall well-being. Using simple random sampling to facilitate representative participation (Rudolph *et al.*, 2023), researchers could target adults, aged 18 and older, who have actively participated in Dental Fear Central for a minimum of six months. Informed consent would be acquired from both the chosen participants and the group moderators (The British Psychological Society, 2021). Researchers might design a descriptive survey administered online via Google Forms, incorporating both open-ended and quantitative questions. The survey would focus on gathering detailed feedback on how participation in OSGs affects various aspects of users' lives. Responses to open-ended questions could be coded into themes that best reflect participants' experiences and organised according to similar responses and major themes by thematic analysis. A similar study was conducted for OSGs pertaining to chronic fatigue syndrome and reported by Morehouse *et al.* (2021), as

well as OSGs regarding Tourette syndrome and tic disorders, reported by Perkins, Coulson, and Davies (2020).

- Future research could employ a realist synthesis study design to investigate the impact of OSGs on managing DA. This approach would involve examining how OSGs function by focusing on several key elements: context—the conditions that influence how OSGs operate, such as the type of forum and user engagement; mechanism—the processes through which OSGs provide support, such as emotional and informational support; and outcome—the results achieved by using OSGs, such as reduced anxiety or improved coping strategies. Participants would give their informed consent prior to taking part (The British Psychological Society, 2021). The research would be conducted in five stages: defining the scope by identifying relevant studies from recent years to ensure applicability to current digital health environments; developing initial program theories by engaging stakeholders, including forum users, forum staff, and dental professionals, in online interviews via Zoom to hypothesise how OSGs might impact DA management; searching for evidence by gathering data from relevant databases and grey literature, focusing on online discussion forums; appraising documents by evaluating their relevance and rigor to provide valuable insights into the OSGs' context, mechanisms, and outcomes; and extracting and synthesising data by developing context-mechanism-outcome configurations to articulate how specific contexts and mechanisms lead to particular outcomes. These configurations would be refined through additional online interviews with key stakeholders, such as forum moderators and dental professionals. A similar study was conducted for OSGs related to mental health and reported by Marshall *et al.* (2024).
- Future research could use a longitudinal observational study design to categorise individual engagement with Dental Fear Central and evaluate its impact on DA levels and health. Informed consent would be obtained from both the selected participants and the group moderators before data collection (The British Psychological Society, 2021). Participants could be classified into three categories:

superusers, who are highly active and frequently post or interact within the community; top contributors, who regularly post and contribute valuable content but are less active than superusers; and contributors, who have made at least one post, indicating some level of engagement with the community. Linear mixed models could then analyse the associations between these engagement levels and changes in DA, as measured by the modified dental anxiety scale (MDAS), and oral health-related quality of life (OHRQoL), as measured by OHIP-14, over a 6-month period, using online questionnaires via Google Forms at baseline and follow-up. A similar study was conducted for OSGs involving depression and anxiety and was reported by Geramita *et al.* (2018).

- Future research could adopt both deductive quantitative and qualitative content analysis, using the SSBC, to explore the types and frequencies of social support sought across OSGs beyond discussion forums, such as Facebook groups, by examining all messages posted during a chosen time period or selecting a predetermined number of messages (Smedley and Coulson, 2018). This method aims to increase the understanding of support-seeking behaviours amongst individuals with DA within OSGs. For example, the content analysis conducted by Pham *et al.* (2024) on diabetes-related Facebook groups and a similar study by Da Moura Semedo, Bath, and Zhang (2023) on discussion forums illustrate that seeking informational support is a predominant type of social support across both platforms, adding to the knowledge of how social support is utilised in several online settings.

6.2.2 Future practice/policy development

- Future practice and policy development could introduce a support system that includes a secure messaging platform for confidential communication between patients and oral health professionals. This system would feature an online discussion forum that is free and accessible to anyone with internet access, similar to Dental Fear Central bulletin board, where users can post asynchronously.

Additionally, a resource toolbox would offer information about DA and local support services. Patients would have exclusive access to their own content, whilst oral health professionals could review relevant information remotely to enhance support. In-person meetings could be held monthly to foster face-to-face interactions and community building. Both the online forum and meetings would be moderated by a trained peer support consultant with personal experience of DA. A similar practice, called ReConnect, is conducted for mental health care and reported by Strand, Eng, and Gammon (2020).

- Future practice and policy development should emphasise that oral health professionals invite individuals with DA to discuss their online activities during consultations. This dialogue may provide insights into the knowledge gathered online, such as information from OSGs, and its impact on managing DA. A similar approach was suggested for Parkinson's disease and reported by Bayen *et al.* (2021).
- Future practice and policy development could create opportunities for individuals to engage with oral health experts online, alongside their online peer support groups, which may improve their access to accurate information about DA (Stangvaltaite-Mouhat *et al.*, 2023).
- Future practice and policy development could encourage policymakers in regions with high prevalence of DA to promote the use of OSGs as a complementary resource alongside formal treatment services. Participation in these groups has been reported to reduce DA levels over an 8-week period, measured by MDAS, amongst adults aged 16–64, with a majority of females from the United States, United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, and Germany, as indicated by Coulson and Buchanan (2007). This strategy mirrors recommendations made for OSGs related to mental health issues in Singapore, where approximately 14% of adults are reported to experience at least one mood, anxiety, or alcohol use disorder at some point in their lives, as discussed by Roystonn *et al.* (2020).

References

Aardal, V. *et al.* (2022) 'The complexity of dental anxiety and its association with oral health-related quality of life: an exploratory study', *European Journal of Oral Sciences*, pp. 1–8. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/eos.12907>

Aartman, I.H.A. *et al.* (2000) 'Dental anxiety reduction and dental attendance after treatment in a dental fear clinic: a follow-up study', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 28(6), pp. 435–442. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0528.2000.028006435.x>

Abrahamsson, K.H. *et al.* (2002) 'Ambivalence in coping with dental fear and avoidance: a qualitative study', *Journal of Health Psychology*, 7(6), pp. 653–664. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1359105302007006869>

Abusulttan, S. (2020) *Assessing social support types and their frequencies in an online support group for dentally anxious individuals*. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362745616_Assessing_social_support_types_and_their_frequencies_in_an_online_support_group_for_dentally_anxious_individuals (Accessed: 23 July 2024).

Adams, P.F. *et al.* (1999) 'Current estimates from the National Health Interview Survey, 1996', *Vital and Health Statistics*. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15782448/> (Accessed: 27 August 2024).

Agras, S., Sylvester, D. and Oliveau, D. (1969) 'The epidemiology of common fears and phobia', *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, 10(2), pp. 151–156. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-440x\(69\)90022-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-440x(69)90022-4)

Al Gtewi, E. (2015) 'Exploring the experiences of individuals with head and neck cancer using online support groups', *White Rose eTheses Online*. Available at: <https://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/10663/> (Accessed: 26 March 2024).

Alabdulkarim, Y. *et al.* (2022) 'Predicting no-shows for dental appointments', *PeerJ Computer Science*, 8, pp. 1–24. doi:<https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1147>

Aldosari, M. *et al.* (2021) 'Factors associated with oral pain and oral health-related productivity loss in the USA, National Health and Nutrition Examination Surveys (NHANES), 2015–2018', *PLOS ONE*, 16(10), pp. 1–14. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0258268>

Algtewi, E.E., Owens, J. and Baker, S.R. (2015) 'Analysing people with head and neck cancers' use of online support groups', *Cyberpsychology: Journal of Psychosocial Research on Cyberspace*, 9(4), pp. 1–20. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5817/cp2015-4-6>

Al-Shammari, K.F. *et al.* (2007) 'Barriers to seeking preventive dental care by Kuwaiti adults', *Medical Principles and Practice*, 16(6), pp. 413–419. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1159/000107733>

Alyami, Y. *et al.* (2020) 'Dental anxiety & phobia: prevalence and most frequent causes among dentists and public in Saudi Arabia', *International Journal of Medicine in Developing Countries*, pp. 325–330. doi:<https://doi.org/10.24911/ijmdc.51-1575237865>

Anawade, P.A., Sharma, D. and Gahane, S. (2024) 'Connecting health and technology: a comprehensive review of social media and online communities in healthcare', *Cureus*, 16(3), pp. 1–9. doi:<https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.55361>

Andersen, L.M.B. *et al.* (2021) 'The social route to mental health: a systematic review and synthesis of theories linking social relationships to mental health to inform interventions', *SSM - Mental Health*, 1(1), pp. 1–15.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmmh.2021.100042>

Antonoplis, S. (2022) 'Studying socioeconomic status: conceptual problems and an alternative path forward', *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 18(2), pp. 275–292.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/17456916221093615>

Appukuttan, D. (2016) 'Strategies to manage patients with dental anxiety and dental phobia: literature review', *Clinical, Cosmetic and Investigational Dentistry*, 8(1), pp. 35–50.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.2147/ccide.s63626>

Armangau, Y. and Figeac, J. (2021) 'Social support networks within transgender Facebook groups: facing a 'therapeutic shield' in France', *Advances in gender research*, pp. 207–222. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/s1529-212620210000032014>

Armfield, J.M. (2010a) 'How do we measure dental fear and what are we measuring anyway?', *Quintessenz Verlags-GmbH*. Available at: <https://www.quintessence-publishing.com/deu/de/article/841676/oral-health-and-preventive-dentistry/2010/02/how-do-we-measure-dental-fear-and-what-are-we-measuring-anyway> (Accessed: 11 August 2024).

Armfield, J.M. (2010b) 'Development and psychometric evaluation of the index of dental anxiety and fear (IDAF-4C+)', *Psychological assessment*, 22(2), pp. 279–87.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0018678>

Armfield, J.M. (2010c) 'The extent and nature of dental fear and phobia in Australia', *Australian Dental Journal*, 55(4), pp. 368–377. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1834-7819.2010.01256.x>

Armfield, J.M. (2012) 'What goes around comes around: revisiting the hypothesized vicious cycle of dental fear and avoidance', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 41(3), pp. 279–287. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdoe.12005>

Armfield, J.M. (2013) 'Predicting dental avoidance among dentally fearful Australian adults', *European Journal of Oral Sciences*, 121(3), pp. 240–246. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/eos.12036>

Armfield, J.M. and Marek, C.L. (2017) 'Patients who are anxious or fearful', in Stefanac, S.J. and Nesbit, S.P. (eds.) *Diagnosis and treatment planning in dentistry*. 3rd edn. Missouri: Elsevier, pp. 323–341.

Armfield, J.M., Spencer, A.J. and Stewart, J. (2006) 'Dental fear in Australia: who's afraid of the dentist?', *Australian Dental Journal*, 51(1), pp. 78–85. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1834-7819.2006.tb00405.x>

Armfield, J.M., Stewart, J.F. and Spencer, A.J. (2007) 'The vicious cycle of dental fear: exploring the interplay between oral health, service utilization and dental fear', *BMC Oral Health*, 7(1), pp. 1–15. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6831-7-1>

Kildahl, A.N. *et al.* (2024) 'A call for trauma-informed dental care for individuals with intellectual disabilities', *Special care in dentistry*, 44(4), pp. 959–1304. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/scd.12959>

Astrom, A.N., Agdal, M.L. and Sulo, G. (2022) 'Exploring avoidance of dental care due to dental fear and economic burden –a cross-sectional study in a national sample of younger adults in Norway', *International Journal of Dental Hygiene*, pp. 1–10. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/idh.12657>

Australian Research Centre for Popu (2012) 'Productivity losses from dental problems', *Australian Dental Journal*, 57(3), pp. 393–397.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1834-7819.2012.01718.x>

Balan, S. (2021) 'English as the language of research: but are we missing the mark?', *Exploratory Research in Clinical and Social Pharmacy*, 3, pp. 1–2.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcsop.2021.100043>

Bandelow, B. and Michaelis, S. (2015) 'Epidemiology of anxiety disorders in the 21st century', *Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience*, 17(3), pp. 327–335.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.31887/dcns.2015.17.3/bbandelow>

Barrera, M. (1986) 'Distinctions between social support concepts, measures, and models', *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 14(4), pp. 413–445.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00922627>

Barrera, M., Sandler, I.N. and Ramsay, T.B. (1981) 'Preliminary development of a scale of social support: studies on college students', *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 9(4), pp. 435–447. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00918174>

Bayen, S. *et al.* (2021) 'Parkinson's disease: content analysis of patient online discussion forums. A prospective observational study using netnography', *Patient Education and Counseling*, 104(8), pp. 2060–2066.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2021.01.028>

Berggren, U. and Meynert, G. (1984) 'Dental fear and avoidance: causes, symptoms, and consequences', *The Journal of the American Dental Association*, 109(2), pp. 247–251. doi:<https://doi.org/10.14219/jada.archive.1984.0328>

Bhatt, S. *et al.* (2018) 'Social determinants of dental anxiety and utilization of oral health services among young adults in Mangalore city, India', *Journal of Indian*

Association of Public Health Dentistry, 16(4), pp. 1–6.

doi:https://doi.org/10.4103/jiaphd.jiaphd_80_18

Blazer, D., Hughes, D. and George, L.K. (1987) 'Stressful life events and the onset of a generalized anxiety syndrome', *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 144(9), pp. 1178–1183. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1176/ajp.144.9.1178>

Braithwaite, D.O., Waldron, V.R. and Finn, J. (1999) 'Communication of social support in computer-mediated groups for people with disabilities', *Health Communication*, 11(2), pp. 123–151. doi:https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327027hc1102_2

Breslau, N. *et al.* (1999) 'Vulnerability to assaultive violence: further specification of the sex difference in post-traumatic stress disorder', *Psychological Medicine*, 29(4), pp. 813–821. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291799008612>

Buchanan, H. and Coulson, N.S. (2007) 'Accessing dental anxiety online support groups: an exploratory qualitative study of motives and experiences', *Patient Education and Counseling*, 66(3), pp. 263–269. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2006.12.011>

Buchanan, H., Coulson, N.S. and Malik, S. (2010) 'Health-related internet support groups and dental anxiety: the fearful patient's online journey', *International Journal of Web Based Communities*, 6(4), pp. 362–375. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1504/ijwbc.2010.035839>

Burles, M.C. and Bally, J.M.G. (2018) 'Ethical, practical, and methodological considerations for unobtrusive qualitative research about personal narratives shared on the internet', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 17(1), pp. 1–9. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406918788203>

Bussey, L.G. and Sillence, E. (2019) 'The role of internet resources in health decision-making: a qualitative study', *DIGITAL HEALTH*, 5, pp. 1–13.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/2055207619888073>

Callen, S. and Oxlad, M. (2024) 'Support sought and offered online for miscarriage: content analysis of a Facebook miscarriage support group', *Psychology and Health*, pp. 1–20. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/08870446.2024.2382790>

CareQuest Institute for Oral Health (2022) *Family affair: a snapshot of oral health disparities and challenges in individuals in households experiencing disability*.

Available at: <https://www.carequest.org/resource-library/family-affair-snapshot-oral-health-disparities-and-challenges-individuals> (Accessed: 27 August 2024).

Carter, A.E. *et al.* (2014) 'Pathways of fear and anxiety in dentistry: a review', *World Journal of Clinical Cases*, 2(11), pp. 1–13.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.12998/wjcc.v2.i11.642>

Chadwick, A., Hall, N.-A. and Vaccari, C. (2023) 'Misinformation rules!? Could 'group rules' reduce misinformation in online personal messaging?', *New Media & Society*, pp. 1–21. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448231172964>

Chalmers, N.I. *et al.* (2017) 'Improving health in the United States', *The Journal of the American Dental Association*, 148(7), pp. 477–480.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adaj.2017.04.031>

Chanpong, B., Haas, D.A. and Locker, D. (2005) 'Need and demand for sedation or general anesthesia in dentistry: a national survey of the Canadian population', *Anesthesia Progress*, 52(1), pp. 3–11. doi:[https://doi.org/10.2344/0003-3006\(2005\)52\[3:nadfso\]2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.2344/0003-3006(2005)52[3:nadfso]2.0.co;2)

Cheung, B.T. *et al.* (2022) 'Dental anxiety among the adult residents of Barangay Cambaog, Bustos, Bulacan, Philippines', *Philippine Journal of Health Research and Development*. Available at: <https://pjhrd.upm.edu.ph/index.php/main/article/view/590> (Accessed: 25 August 2024).

Cheung, K.K.C. and Tai, K.W.H. (2021) 'The use of intercoder reliability in qualitative interview data analysis in science education', *Research in Science & Technological Education*, 41(3), pp. 1–21. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/02635143.2021.1993179>

Chew, A.M.K. and Gunasekeran, D.V. (2021) 'Social media big data: the good, the bad, and the ugly (un)truths', *Frontiers in Big Data*, 4, pp. 1–4. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fdata.2021.623794>

Coe, K. and Scacco, J.M. (2017) 'Content analysis, quantitative', in Matthes, J., Davis, C.S. and Potter, R.F. (eds.) *The international encyclopedia of communication research methods*. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, pp. 1–11.

Cohen, S. and McKay, G. (1984) 'Social support, stress and the buffering hypothesis: a theoretical analysis', in Baum, A. S., Taylor, E. and Singer, J. E. (eds.) *Handbook of psychology and health*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum, pp. 253–267.

Cohen, S. and Wills, T.A. (1985) 'Stress, social support, and the buffering hypothesis', *Psychological Bulletin*, 98(2), pp. 310–357. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.98.2.310>

Cohen, S.M., Fiske, J. and Newton, J.T. (2000) 'The impact of dental anxiety on daily living', *British Dental Journal*, 189(7), pp. 385–390. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.bdj.4800777>

Cohen, S., Underwood, L.G. and Gottlieb, B.H. (2000) 'Social relationships and health', in Cohen, S., Underwood, L.G. and Gottlieb, B.H. (eds.) *Social support*

measurement and intervention: a guide for health and social scientists. New York: Oxford University Press, pp. 3–26.

Costa, F.S. *et al.* (2018) 'Anxiety symptoms have a direct effect on oral health perception in young women', *Quality of Life Research*, 27(6), pp. 1583–1588. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-018-1797-4>

Coulson, N.S. (2005) 'Receiving social support online: an analysis of a computer-mediated support group for individuals living with irritable bowel syndrome', *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 8(6), pp. 580–584. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1089/cpb.2005.8.580>

Coulson, N.S. (2018) 'Online support communities', in Atrill-Smith, A., Fullwood, C., Keep, M. and Kuss, D.J. (eds.) *The oxford handbook of cyberpsychology*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 239–260.

Coulson, N.S. and Buchanan, H. (2007) 'Self-reported efficacy of an online dental anxiety support group: a pilot study', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 36(1), pp. 43–46 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0528.2007.00349.x>

Coulson, N.S. and Buchanan, H. (2022) 'The role of online support groups in helping individuals affected by HIV and AIDS: scoping review of the literature', *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 24(7), pp. 1–19. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/27648>

Coulson, N.S. and Greenwood, N. (2011) 'Families affected by childhood cancer: an analysis of the provision of social support within online support groups', *Child: Care, Health and Development*, 38(6), pp. 870–877. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2214.2011.01316.x>

Coulson, N.S., Buchanan, H. and Aubeeluck, A. (2007) 'Social support in cyberspace: a content analysis of communication within a Huntington's disease online support

group', *Patient Education and Counseling*, 68(2), pp. 173–178.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2007.06.002>

Coulson, N.S., Bullock, E. and Rodham, K. (2017) 'Exploring the therapeutic affordances of self-harm online support communities: an online survey of members', *JMIR Mental Health*, 4(4), pp. 1–11. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/mental.8084>

Coursaris, C.K. and Liu, M. (2009) 'An analysis of social support exchanges in online HIV/AIDS self-help groups', *Computers in Human Behavior*, 25(4), pp. 911–918. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2009.03.006>

Crawford, A.N., Hawker, B.J. and Lennon, M.A. (1997) 'A dental support group for anxious patients', *British Dental Journal*. Available at:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18069179/> (Accessed: 11 April 2024).

Cutrona, C. E. and Russell, D.W. (1990) 'Type of social support and specific stress: toward a theory of optimal matching', in Sarason, B.R., Sarason, I.G. and Pierce, G.R. (eds.) *Social support: an interactional review*. New York: John Wiley & Sons, pp. 319–366.

Cutrona, C.E. and Suhr, J.A. (1992) 'Controllability of stressful events and satisfaction with spouse support behaviors', *Communication Research*, 19(2), pp. 154–174. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/009365092019002002>

Da Moura Semedo, C., Bath, P.A. and Zhang, Z. (2023) 'Social support in a diabetes online community: mixed methods content analysis', *JMIR Diabetes*, 8, pp. 1–12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/41320>

Davey, G.C.L. (1989) 'Dental phobias and anxieties: evidence for conditioning processes in the acquisition and modulation of a learned fear', *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 27(1), pp. 51–58. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967\(89\)90119-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967(89)90119-8)

Davies, M. *et al.* (2016) 'Large-scale no-show patterns and distributions for clinic operational research', *Healthcare*, 4(1), pp. 1–12.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare4010015>

Daynes-Kearney, R. and Gallagher, S. (2023) 'Online support groups for family caregivers: scoping review', *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 25, pp. 1–19.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/46858>

de Jonge, P. *et al.* (2016) 'Cross-national epidemiology of panic disorder and panic attacks in the world mental health surveys', *Depression and Anxiety*, 33(12), pp. 1155–1177. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/da.22572>

Delgado-Angulo, E.K. *et al.* (2015) 'The association of depression and anxiety with dental caries and periodontal disease among Finnish adults', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 43(6), pp. 540–549. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdoe.12179>

Dental Fear Central (2024) *Forum*. Available at: <https://www.dentalfearcentral.org/> (Accessed: 27 July 2024).

Diaz, T. *et al.* (2021) 'A call for standardised age-disaggregated health data', *The Lancet Healthy Longevity*, 2(7), pp. 436–443. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/s2666-7568\(21\)00115-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2666-7568(21)00115-x)

Dikshit, P., Limbu, S. and Bhattarai, K. (2013) 'Evaluation of dental anxiety in parents accompanying their children for dental treatment', *Orthodontic Journal of Nepal*, 3(1), pp. 47–52. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3126/ojn.v3i1.9282>

Dimitriou, C., Schmidt, K.L. and Li, H. (2024) 'Factors influencing dental anxiety using a modified dental anxiety scale (MDAS)', *Archives of dentistry and oral health*, 5(1), pp. 1–16. doi:<https://doi.org/10.22259/2638-4809.0501001>

Dodemaide, P. *et al.* (2021) 'Therapeutic affordances of social media and associated quality of life outcomes in young adults', *Social Science Computer Review*, pp. 44–63. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/08944393211032940>

Dou, L. *et al.* (2018) 'The prevalence of dental anxiety and its association with pain and other variables among adult patients with irreversible pulpitis', *BMC Oral Health*, 18(1), pp. 1–6. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-018-0563-x>

Duffin, S.J. (2024) 'The role of informational support in online groups for people on the autism spectrum', *White Rose eTheses Online*. Available at: <https://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/34645/> (Accessed: 12 April 2024).

Eachempati, P. *et al.* (2019) 'Management of gag reflex for patients undergoing dental treatment', *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 11, pp. 1–56. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd011116.pub3>

Eichhorn, K.C. (2008) 'Soliciting and providing social support over the internet: an investigation of online eating disorder support groups', *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 14(1), pp. 67–78. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2008.01431.x>

Eitner, S. *et al.* (2006) 'Dental anxiety - an epidemiological study on its clinical correlation and effects on oral health', *Journal of Oral Rehabilitation*, 33(8), pp. 588–593. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2842.2005.01589.x>

Eklund, L. *et al.* (2021) 'Beyond a dichotomous understanding of online anonymity: bridging the macro and micro level', *Sociological Research Online*, 27(2), pp. 1–18. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/13607804211019760>

El Hajj, K. H., Fares, Y. and Abou-Abbas, L. (2021) 'Assessment of dental anxiety and dental phobia among adults in Lebanon', *BMC Oral Health*, 21(1), pp. 1–10.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-021-01409-2>

Eli, I. (1993) 'Dental anxiety: a cause for possible misdiagnosis of tooth vitality', *International Endodontic Journal*, 26(4), pp. 251–253.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2591.1993.tb00567.x>

Emrani, R. *et al.* (2021) 'Job satisfaction among dentists according to workplace in Tehran', *Frontiers in Dentistry*, 18(11), pp. 1–7.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.18502/fid.v18i11.6136>

Erazo, R. *et al.* (2018) 'Validity and reliability of the index of dental anxiety and fear (IDAF-4C+) in Chilean pregnant women', *Avances en Odontoestomatología*.

Available at: https://scielo.isciii.es/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0213-12852018000500001 (Accessed: 25 August 2024).

Erlingsson, C. and Brysiewicz, P. (2017) 'A hands-on guide to doing content analysis', *African Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 7(3), pp. 93–99.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.afjem.2017.08.001>

Eroglu, C., Ataoglu, H. and Kucuk, K. (2016) 'Factors affecting anxiety-fear of surgical procedures in dentistry', *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice*, pp. 1–6.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.4103/1119-3077.181371>

Falgoust, G. *et al.* (2022) 'Applying the uses and gratifications theory to identify motivational factors behind young adult's participation in viral social media challenges on TikTok', *Human Factors in Healthcare*, 2(100014), pp. 1–14.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hfh.2022.100014>

Fallea, A., Zuccarello, R. and Cali, F. (2016) 'Dental anxiety in patients with borderline intellectual functioning and patients with intellectual disabilities', *BMC Oral Health*, 16(1), pp. 1–6. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-016-0312-y>

Festinger, L. (1954) 'A theory of social comparison processes', *Human Relations*, 7(2), pp. 117–140. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/001872675400700202>

Friedman, E.M. *et al.* (2018) 'Online peer support groups for family caregivers: are they reaching the caregivers with the greatest needs?', *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 25(9), pp. 1130–1136. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocy086>

Gammon, D. *et al.* (2017) 'Shifting practices toward recovery-oriented care through an e-recovery portal in community mental health care: a mixed-methods exploratory study', *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 19(5), pp. 1–15. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.7524>

Geramita, E.M. *et al.* (2018) 'The association between increased levels of patient engagement with an internet support group and improved mental health outcomes at 6-month follow-up: post-hoc analyses from a randomized controlled trial', *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 20(7), pp. 1–11. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/10402>

Germain, J. *et al.* (2017) 'Why should we use online research methods? Four doctoral health student perspectives', *Qualitative Health Research*, 28(10), pp. 1650–1657. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732317721698>

Ghaffar, A. *et al.* (2024) 'Impact of high-speed handpiece noise-induced dental anxiety on heart rate: analyzing experienced and non-experienced patients - a comparative study', *BMC oral health*, 24(1), pp. 1–7. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-024-04017-y>

- Gheyle, N. and Jacobs, T. (2017) 'Content analysis: a short overview', *Internal research note*, pp. 1–18. doi:<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33689.31841>
- Gibson, J. (1986) 'The theory of affordances', *The ecological approach to visual perceptions*. Hillsdale, New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, pp. 127–137.
- Gilbert, P.A. *et al.* (2022) 'Gender differences in lifetime and current use of online support for recovery from alcohol use disorder', *Alcoholism: Clinical and Experimental Research*, 46(6), pp. 1073–1083. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/acer.14827>
- Goetz, K., Schuldei, R. and Steinhauser, J. (2018) 'Working conditions, job satisfaction and challenging encounters in dentistry: a cross-sectional study', *International Dental Journal*, 69(1), pp. 44–49. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/idj.12414>
- Gremigni, P. *et al.* (2014) 'Validation of the modified dental anxiety scale (MDAS) in an Italian sample and invariance across gender and mode of administration', *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, 30(2), pp. 140–149.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1027/1015-5759/a000182>
- Griffiths, K.M. (2017) 'Mental health internet support groups: just a lot of talk or a valuable intervention?', *World Psychiatry*, 16(3), pp. 247–248.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/wps.20444>
- Grundy, Q. *et al.* (2020) 'Promotion or education: a content analysis of industry-authored oral health educational materials targeted at acute care nurses', *BMJ Open*, 10(11), pp. 1–10. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-040541>
- Guentsch, A. *et al.* (2016) 'Oral health and dental anxiety in a German practice-based sample', *Clinical Oral Investigations*, 21(5), pp. 1675–1680.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00784-016-1951-8>

Ha, J.-E. and Ye, K.-H. (2019) 'The effect of participation of clinical dental hygiene care program on the level of dental fear in some adults', *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*, 10(11), pp. 4412–4412.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.5958/0976-5506.2019.04302.x>

Haardorfer, R. (2019) 'Taking quantitative data analysis out of the positivist era: calling for theory-driven data-informed analysis', *Health Education & Behavior*, 46(4), pp. 537–540. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1090198119853536>

Hai, A.H. *et al.* (2021) 'Trends and correlates of Internet support group participation for mental health problems in the United States, 2004–2018', *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 132, pp. 136–143. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2020.10.012>

Hakeberg, M. and Berggren, U. (1993) 'Changes in sick leave among Swedish dental patients after treatment for dental fear', *Community Dental Health*. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8495390/> (Accessed: 19 August 2024).

Hale, B.J. (2019) 'Responding to depression-related Imgur posts: a content analysis of social support and non-bona fide features in user-generated comments', *DIGITAL HEALTH*, 5, pp. 1–12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/2055207619890476>

Hallett, R.E. and Barber, K. (2013) 'Ethnographic research in a cyber era', *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography*, 43(3), pp. 306–330.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0891241613497749>

Halonon, H. *et al.* (2018) 'The association between dental anxiety and psychiatric disorders and symptoms: a systematic review', *Clinical Practice and Epidemiology in Mental Health*, 14(1), pp. 1–16. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2174/1745017901814010207>

Hamid, R. *et al.* (2018) 'State and trait anxiety evaluation in dental patients', *International Journal of Depression and Anxiety*, 1(1), pp. 1–6.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.23937/ijda-2017/1710008>

Hanley, T., Prescott, J. and Gomez, K.U. (2019) 'A systematic review exploring how young people use online forums for support around mental health issues', *Journal of Mental Health*, 28(5), pp. 566–576.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/09638237.2019.1630725>

Harris, J. *et al.* (2024) 'Ethical guidance for conducting health research with online communities: a scoping review of existing guidance', *PloS one*, 19(5), pp. 1–19.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0302924>

Hassan, B.H. *et al.* (2022) 'Dental anxiety and oral-health-related quality of life among rural community-dwelling older adults', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(13), pp. 1–13.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19137643>

Hmud, R. and Walsh, L. (2007) 'Dental anxiety: causes, complications and management approaches', *International Dentistry SA*. Available at:
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Dental-anxiety%3A-causes%2C-complications-and-Hmud-Walsh/7269d14d5cb034fefe632a609eb0dc354f226341>
(Accessed: 23 August 2024).

Hsieh, H.F. and Shannon, S.E. (2005) 'Three approaches to qualitative content analysis', *Qualitative Health Research*, 15(9), pp. 1277–1288.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732305276687>

Huang, Y.-H.C., Wu, F. and Huang, Q. (2017) 'Does research on digital public relations indicate a paradigm shift? An analysis and critique of recent trends',

Telematics and Informatics, 34(7), pp. 1364–1376.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2016.08.012>

Humble, N. and Mozelius, P. (2022) 'Content analysis or thematic analysis: similarities, differences and applications in qualitative research', *European Conference on Research Methodology for Business and Management Studies*, 21(1), pp. 76–81.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.34190/ecrm.21.1.316>

Hwang, S. and Foote, J.D. (2021) 'Why do people participate in small online communities?', *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 5(2), pp. 1–25.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1145/3479606>

John, M. *et al.* (2022) 'Recommendations for use and scoring of oral health impact profile versions', *Journal of Evidence-Based Dental Practice*, 22(1), pp. 1–10.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jebdp.2021.101619>

Johns, R. and Jepsen, D. (2015) 'Sources of occupational stress in NSW and ACT dentists', *Australian Dental Journal*, 60(2), pp. 182–189.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/adj.12323>

Jones, K., Merrick, J. and Beasley, C. (2016) 'A content analysis of oral health messages in Australian mass media', *Australian Dental Journal*, 61(1), pp. 16–20.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/adj.12300>

Kleinheksel, A.J. *et al.* (2020) 'Demystifying content analysis', *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 84(1), pp. 127–137. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe7113>

Khatoon, B., Hill, K.B. and Walmsley, A.D. (2013) 'Can we learn, teach and practise dentistry anywhere, anytime?', *British Dental Journal*, 215(7), pp. 345–347.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.bdj.2013.957>

Kheir, O.O. *et al.* (2018) 'Patient-dentist relationship and dental anxiety among young Sudanese adult patients', *International Dental Journal*, 69(1), pp. 1–9.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/idj.12409>

Kisely, S. (2016) 'No mental health without oral health', *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, 61(5), pp. 277–282. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0706743716632523>

Krippendorff, K. (2019) 'Conceptual foundation', *Content analysis: an introduction to its methodology*. 4th edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc, pp. 24–50.

Kumar, S. *et al.* (2009) 'Does dental anxiety influence oral health-related quality of life? Observations from a cross-sectional study among adults in Udaipur district, India', *Journal of Oral Science*, 51(2), pp. 245–254.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.2334/josnurd.51.245>

Kumari, M., Sharma, S. and Raj, A. (2023) 'Factors contributing to dental anxiety and fear in dental procedures – an exploratory study', *Journal of Advanced Sciences*, 2(1), pp. 1–6. doi:<https://doi.org/10.58935/joas.v2i1.28>

Kyngas, H., Kaakinen, P. (2020) 'Deductive content analysis', in Kyngas, H., Mikkonen, K. and Kaariainen, M. (eds.) *The application of content analysis in nursing science research*. Switzerland: Springer, pp. 23–30.

Latkovikj, T. M. and Poposvka, B.M. (2020) 'Online research about online research: advantages and disadvantages', *E-methodology*, 6(6), pp. 44–56.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.15503/emet2019.44.56>

Lautch, H. (1971) 'Dental phobia', *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 119(549), pp. 151–158. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.119.549.151>

Lee, J.K. (2020) 'The effects of social comparison orientation on psychological well-being in social networking sites: serial mediation of perceived social support and self-esteem', *Current Psychology*, 41(9), pp. 6247–6259.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-020-01114-3>

Levin, L. *et al.* (2018) 'Demographic profile, oral health impact profile and dental anxiety scale in patients with chronic periodontitis: a case–control study',

International Dental Journal, 68(4), pp. 269–278.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/idj.12381>

Liau, T.T. (2022) 'Content analysis and its application with dynamic online content',

Jurnal Teknik Industri, 24(2), pp. 105–116. doi:<https://doi.org/10.9744/jti.24.2.105-116>

Liinavuori, A. *et al.* (2019) 'Longitudinal interrelationships between dental fear and dental attendance among adult Finns in 2000-2011', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 47(4), pp. 309–315. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdoe.12458>

Lin, T. *et al.* (2015) 'Exploring the relationship between receiving and offering online social support: a dual social support model', *Information & Management*, 52(3), pp.

371–383. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2015.01.003>

Lindsay, S.J.E., Wege, P. and Yates, J. (1984) 'Expectations of sensations, discomfort and fear in dental treatment', *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 22(2), pp. 99–108.

doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967\(84\)90098-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967(84)90098-6)

Liu, J. and Wang, J. (2021) 'Users' intention to continue using online mental health communities: empowerment theory perspective', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(18), pp. 1–17.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18189427>

Liu, W. *et al.* (2019) 'Perceived community support, users' interactions, and value co-creation in online health community: the moderating effect of social exclusion', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(1), pp. 1–22. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17010204>

Locker, D. (2003) 'Psychosocial consequences of dental fear and anxiety', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 31(2), pp. 144–151. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0528.2003.00028.x>

Locker, D. *et al.* (1999) 'Age of onset of dental anxiety', *Journal of Dental Research*, 78(3), pp. 790–796. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/00220345990780031201>

Locker, D., Poulton, R. and Thomson, W.M. (2001) 'Psychological disorders and dental anxiety in a young adult population', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 29(6), pp. 456–463. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0528.2001.290607.x>

Locker, D., Shapiro, D. and Liddell, A. (1996) 'Negative dental experiences and their relationship to dental anxiety', *Community Dental Health*. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8763138/> (Accessed: 19 August 2024).

Lopes, C.T. and Barbara, S. (2019) *A classification scheme for analyses of messages exchanged in online health forums*. Poland, 9–11 October. Available at: <https://www.informationr.net/ir/24-1/isic2018/isic1827.html> (Accessed: 31 August 2024).

Lotto, M. *et al.* (2023) 'Exploring online oral health misinformation: a content analysis', *Brazilian Oral Research*, 37, pp. 1–12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1590/1807-3107bor-2023.vol37.0049>

Malinen, S. (2015) 'Understanding user participation in online communities: a systematic literature review of empirical studies', *Computers in Human Behavior*, 46, pp. 228–238. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.01.004>

Malloch, Y., Zhang, J. and Qian, S. (2023) 'Effects of social comparison direction, comparison distance, and message framing on health behavioral intention in online support groups', *Cyberpsychology*, 17(3), pp. 1–17.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.5817/cp2023-3-10>

Marmot, M. G. and Wilkinson, R. D. (2006) 'Social determinants of health', *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 35(4), pp. 1111–1112.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyl121>

Marshall, P. *et al.* (2024) 'Understanding the impacts of online mental health peer support forums: realist synthesis', *JMIR Mental Health*, 11(1), pp. 1–18.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/55750>

Marteinsdottir, I. *et al.* (2007) 'The role of life events in social phobia', *Nordic Journal of Psychiatry*, 61(3), pp. 207–212. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/08039480701352546>

Martin, M.D., Kinoshita-Byrne, J. and Getz, T. (2002) 'Dental fear in a special needs clinic population of persons with disabilities', *Special Care in Dentistry*, 22(3), pp.

99–102. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1754-4505.2002.tb01170.x>

McGrath, C. and Bedi, R. (2004) 'The association between dental anxiety and oral health-related quality of life in Britain', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*,

32(1), pp. 67–72. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0528.2004.00119.x>

Minja, I.K. and Kahabuka, F.K. (2019) 'Dental anxiety and its consequences to oral health care attendance and delivery', in Kocabasoglu, N. and Caglayan, H. (eds.) *Anxiety disorders - from childhood to adulthood*. London, UK: IntechOpen, pp. 35–50.

Mittelmark, M.B. (1999) 'Social ties and health promotion: suggestions for population-based research', *Health Education Research*, 14(4), pp. 447–451.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/her/14.4.447>

Mo, P.K.H. and Coulson, N.S. (2008) 'Exploring the communication of social support within virtual communities: a content analysis of messages posted to an online HIV/AIDS support group', *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 11(3), pp. 371–374.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1089/cpb.2007.0118>

Moore, R. and Bering, P. (2017) 'Dental anxiety among Danish adults—comparison of recent website data and older telephone data with government demographic statistics', *Open Journal of Stomatology*, 7(12), pp. 530–544.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.4236/ojst.2017.712050>

Moore, R. and Brodsgaard, I. (2001) 'Dentists' perceived stress and its relation to perceptions about anxious patients', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 29(1), pp. 73–80. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0528.2001.00011.x>

Moreton, J., Kelly, C.S. and Sandstrom, G.M. (2023) 'Social support from weak ties: insight from the literature on minimal social interactions', *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 17(3), pp. 1–12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/spc3.12729>

Morehouse, S. *et al.* (2021) 'Impacts of online support groups on quality of life, and perceived anxiety and depression in those with ME/CFS: a survey', *Fatigue: Biomedicine, Health & Behavior*, 9(2), pp. 113–122.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/21641846.2021.1950406>

Muneer, M.U. *et al.* (2022) 'Dental anxiety and influencing factors in adults', *Healthcare*, 10(12), pp. 1–7. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10122352>

Murad, M., Ingle, N. and Assery, M. (2020) 'Evaluating factors associated with fear and anxiety to dental treatment—a systematic review', *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 9(9), pp. 1–6. doi:https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmipc.jfmipc_607_20

Musalam, K. *et al.* (2021) 'Magnitude and determinants of dental anxiety among adult patients attending public dental clinics in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania', *International Journal of Dentistry*, pp. 1–7. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9965204>

Naslund, J.A. *et al.* (2020) 'Social media and mental health: benefits, risks, and opportunities for research and practice', *Journal of Technology in Behavioral Science*, 5(3), pp. 245–257. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s41347-020-00134-x>

National Cancer Institute (2020) *Social support*. Available at: <https://cancercontrol.cancer.gov/brp/research/constructs/social-support> (Accessed: 8 March 2024).

Nermo, H. *et al.* (2021) 'Dental anxiety and potentially traumatic events: a cross-sectional study based on the Tromsø Study—Tromsø 7', *BMC Oral Health*, 21(1), pp. 1–13. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-021-01968-4>

Nicolas, E. *et al.* (2007) 'A national cross-sectional survey of dental anxiety in the French adult population', *BMC Oral Health*, 7(1), pp. 1–7. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6831-7-12>

Ninan, J. (2020) 'Online naturalistic inquiry in project management research: directions for research', *Project Leadership and Society*, 1, pp. 1–9. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plas.2020.100002>

Nithya, S. *et al.* (2018) 'Dental anxiety and influencing factors: a cross-sectional questionnaire-based survey', *Indian Journal of Dental Research*, 29(1), pp. 1–6. doi:https://doi.org/10.4103/ijdr.ijdr_33_17

Obeidat, S.R., Alsa'di, A.G. and Taani, D.S. (2014) 'Factors influencing dental care access in Jordanian adults', *BMC Oral Health*, 14(1), pp. 1–7.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6831-14-127>

Office for Health Improvement and Disparities (2024) *Adult oral health survey 2021: service use and barriers to accessing care*. Available at:

<https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/adult-oral-health-survey-2021/adult-oral-health-survey-2021-service-use-and-barriers-to-accessing-care> (Accessed: 28 August 2024).

Ogawa, M., Sago, T. and Furukawa, H. (2020) 'The reliability and validity of the Japanese version of the modified dental anxiety scale among dental outpatients', *The Scientific World Journal*, pp. 1–6. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8734946>

Olawole, W.O. *et al.* (2019) 'Anxiety in a dental and maxillofacial surgery consulting room: does previous experience matter?', *Global Psychiatry*, 2(2), pp. 165–170.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.2478/gp-2019-0014>

Olmos-Vega, F.M. *et al.* (2022) 'A practical guide to reflexivity in qualitative research: AMEE Guide no. 149', *Medical Teacher*, 45(149), pp. 1–11.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159x.2022.2057287>

Oosterink, F.M.D., de Jongh, A. and Aartman, I.H.A. (2009) 'Negative events and their potential risk of precipitating pathological forms of dental anxiety', *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 23(4), pp. 451–457.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2008.09.002>

Oosterink, F.M.D., de Jongh, A. and Hoogstraten, J. (2009) 'Prevalence of dental fear and phobia relative to other fear and phobia subtypes', *European Journal of Oral Sciences*, 117(2), pp. 135–143. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0722.2008.00602.x>

Pan, W. *et al.* (2020) 'What to say when seeking support online: a comparison among different levels of self-disclosure', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, pp. 1–9.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00978>

Papapanou, T.K. *et al.* (2023) 'Strong correlations between social appearance anxiety, use of social media, and feelings of loneliness in adolescents and young adults',

International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 20(5), pp. 1–10.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20054296>

Pearce, K.E. *et al.* (2022) 'Online social support for infertility in Azerbaijan', *New Media & Society*, 26(6), pp. 3107–3126.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448221097946>

Peres, M.A. *et al.* (2019) 'Oral diseases: a global public health challenge', *The Lancet*, 394(10194), pp. 249–260. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(19\)31146-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(19)31146-8)

Perkins, V., Coulson, N.S. and Davies, E.B. (2020) '“We are the real experts”: an online survey exploring users’ experiences of participation in online support communities for Tourette syndrome and tic disorders', *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 22(11), pp. 1–14. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/18099>

Petersen, P.E. (2003) 'The world oral health report 2003: continuous improvement of oral health in the 21st century - the approach of the WHO global oral health programme', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 31(1), pp. 3–24.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1046/j..2003.com122.x>

Petric, G. *et al.* (2023) 'The quality of informational social support in online health communities: a content analysis of cancer-related discussions', *Digital Health*, 9, pp.

1–18. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/20552076231155681>

Petukhova, T.A. *et al.* (2020) 'Utilization of Facebook for support and education by patients with skin cancer', *Dermatology Online Journal*, 26(3), pp. 1–4.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.5070/D3263047973>

Pham, S. *et al.* (2024) 'Help-seeking, support, and engagement in gestational diabetes mellitus online communities on Facebook: content analysis', *JMIR formative research*, 8, pp. 1–6. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/49494>

doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/49494>

Pigott, T.D. (2017) 'The role of theory in quantitative data analysis', *Loyola eCommons*. Available at: https://ecommons.luc.edu/education_facpubs/121/

(Accessed: 6 September 2024).

Pohjola, V. *et al.* (2011) 'Anxiety and depressive disorders and dental fear among adults in Finland', *European Journal of Oral Sciences*, 119(1), pp. 55–60.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0722.2010.00795.x>

Pohjola, V. *et al.* (2014) 'Dental fear, tobacco use and alcohol use among university students in Finland: a national survey', *BMC Oral Health*, 14(1), pp. 1–8.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6831-14-86>

Potter, J. (2002) 'Two kinds of natural', *Discourse Studies*, 4(4), pp. 539–542.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/14614456020040040901>

Pouradeli, S. *et al.* (2016) 'Occupational stress and coping behaviours among dentists in Kerman, Iran', *Sultan Qaboos University Medical Journal*, 16(3), pp. 341–346.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.18295/squmj.2016.16.03.013>

Rachman, S. (1977) 'The conditioning theory of fear acquisition: a critical examination', *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 15(5), pp. 375–387.

doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967\(77\)90041-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967(77)90041-9)

Rado, N. *et al.* (2022) 'Digital technology access and health-related internet use among people experiencing homelessness in Hungary: quantitative survey', *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 24(10), pp. 1–14. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/38729>

Ramseier, C. *et al.* (2023) 'Dental anxiety in Switzerland: trends in prevalence and associations with socioeconomic factors in 2010 and 2017', *Swiss dental journal*, 134(1), pp. 52–71. doi:<https://doi.org/10.61872/sdj-2024-05-01>

Randall, C.L. *et al.* (2016) 'Toward a genetic understanding of dental fear: evidence of heritability', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 45(1), pp. 66–73. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdoe.12261>

Rauch (2019) 'Pain, dental fear, and oral health-related quality of life-patients seeking care in an emergency dental service in Germany', *The journal of contemporary dental practice*. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31058610/> (Accessed: 24 August 2024).

Rayland, A. and Andrews, J. (2023) 'From social network to peer support network: opportunities to explore mechanisms of online peer support for mental health', *JMIR Mental Health*, 10, pp. 1–9. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/41855>

Reading, J.M., Buhr, K.J. and Stuckey, H.L. (2019) 'Social experiences of adults using online support forums to lose weight: a qualitative content analysis', *Health Education & Behavior*, 46(2), pp. 129–133. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1090198119859403>

Reifegerste, D., Wasgien, K. and Hagen, L.M. (2017) 'Online social support for obese adults: exploring the role of forum activity', *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 101, pp. 1–8. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2017.02.003>

Reisine, S.T. (1985) 'Dental health and public policy: the social impact of dental disease', *American Journal of Public Health*, 75(1), pp. 27–30.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.2105/ajph.75.1.27>

Reisine, S.T. *et al.* (1989) 'Impact of dental conditions on patients' quality of life', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 17(1), pp. 7–10.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0528.1989.tb01816.x>

Reisine, S.T. and Miller, J. (1985) 'A longitudinal study of work loss related to dental diseases', *Social Science & Medicine*, 21(12), pp. 1309–1314.

doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536\(85\)90433-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536(85)90433-2)

Rimmel, G. and Cordazzo, M. (2021) 'Deductive vs inductive content analysis – a methodological research note to disclosures studies in intellectual capital research', in Dumay, J., Nielsen, C., Lund, M., Guthrie, J. and Massaro, M. (eds.) *Research handbook on intellectual capital and business*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar, pp. 109–125.

Roest, A.M. *et al.* (2019) 'A comparison of DSM-5 and DSM-IV agoraphobia in the World Mental Health Surveys', *Depression and Anxiety*, 36(6), pp. 499–510.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/da.22885>

Rook, K.S. (1985) 'The functions of social bonds: perspectives from research on social support, loneliness and social isolation', in Sarason, I.G. and Sarason, B.R. (eds.) *Social support: theory, research and applications*. Dordrecht: Springer, pp. 243–267.

Roy-Byrne, P. P., Geraci, M. and Uhde, T.W. (1986) 'Life events and the onset of panic disorder', *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 143(11), pp. 1424–1427.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1176/ajp.143.11.1424>

Roystonn, K. *et al.* (2020) 'The public health impact and policy implications of online support group use for mental health in Singapore: cross-sectional survey', *JMIR Mental Health*, 7(8), pp. 1–12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/18114>

Rudolph, J.E. *et al.* (2023) 'Defining representativeness of study samples in medical and population health research', *BMJ Medicine*, 2(1), pp. 1–7. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjmed-2022-000399>

Ruscio, A.M. *et al.* (2017) 'Cross-sectional comparison of the epidemiology of DSM-5 generalized anxiety disorder across the globe', *JAMA Psychiatry*, 74(5), pp. 465–475. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2017.0056>

Saatchi, M. *et al.* (2015) 'The prevalence of dental anxiety and fear in patients referred to Isfahan Dental School, Iran', *Dental Research Journal*. Available at: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc4432608/> (Accessed 30 July 2024).

Saheer, A. *et al.* (2022) 'Effect of dental anxiety on oral health among the first-time dental visitors: a hospital-based study', *Journal of Pharmacy & Bioallied Sciences*, 14, pp. 394–398. doi:https://doi.org/10.4103/jpbs.jpbs_632_21

Samami, M., Farrahi, H. and Alinia, M. (2024) 'The relationship between dental anxiety and oral health literacy with oral health-related quality of life', *BMC Oral Health*, 24(1), pp. 1–7. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-024-04359-7>

Sato, Y. *et al.* (2022) 'Cross-sectional associations between oral diseases and work productivity loss among regular employees in Japan', *Industrial Health*, 61(1), pp. 3–13. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2486/indhealth.2021-0274>

Schwarzer, R. and Rieckmann, N. (2002) *Social support, cardiovascular disease, and mortality*. Available at: <https://userpage.fu->

berlin.de/~health/support/schwarzer_rieckmann_in_weidner.pdf (Accessed: 26 March 2024).

Sheiham, A. *et al.* (2015) 'Billions with oral disease', *The Journal of the American Dental Association*, 146(12), pp. 861–864.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adaj.2015.09.019>

Shet, R.G.K. *et al.* (2013) 'Association of oral health related quality of life with dental anxiety and depression along with general health among people of Bhopal district, Madhya Pradesh', *Journal of International Oral Health*. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3895711/> (Accessed: 20 August 2024).

Shin, W.K., Braun, T.M. and Inglehart, M.R. (2013) 'Parents' dental anxiety and oral health literacy: effects on parents' and children's oral health-related experiences', *Journal of Public Health Dentistry*, 74(3), pp. 195–201.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/jphd.12046>

Sammith Shetty, S., Shibani Shetty, and Swapna B.V. (2023) 'The relationship between personality traits, dental anxiety, and self-reported bruxism among health professional students: a cross-sectional study', *Journal of Health Sciences*, pp. 1–8.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.17532/jhsci.2023.2203>

Shevchenko, Y. and Reips, U-D. (2023) 'Geofencing in location-based behavioral research: methodology, challenges, and implementation', *Behavior Research Methods*.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-023-02213-2>

Silveira, E.R. *et al.* (2021a) 'Estimated prevalence of dental fear in adults: a systematic review and meta-analysis', *Journal of Dentistry*, 108, pp. 1–10.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdent.2021.103632>

Silveira, E.R. *et al.* (2021b) 'The vicious cycle of dental fear at age 31 in a birth cohort in Southern Brazil', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 49(4), pp. 354–361. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/cdoe.12609>

Sitheequ, M. *et al.* (2014) 'Validation of the Malay version of the modified dental anxiety scale and the prevalence of dental anxiety in a Malaysian population', *Journal of Investigative and Clinical Dentistry*, 6(4), pp. 313–320. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/jicd.12106>

Sivaramakrishnan, G. *et al.* (2022) 'The variables associated with dental anxiety and their management in primary care dental clinics in Bahrain: a cross-sectional study', *BMC oral health*, 22(1), pp. 1–8. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-022-02173-7>

Smedley, R.M. and Coulson, N.S. (2018) 'A practical guide to analysing online support forums', *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 18(1), pp. 1–28. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/14780887.2018.1475532>

Smith, H., Bulbul, A. and Jones, C.J. (2017) 'Can online discussion sites generate quality data for research purposes?' *Frontiers in Public Health*, 5, pp. 1–4. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2017.00156>

Song, Y., Luzzi, L. and Brennan, D. (2023) 'Psychosocial factors, dentist-patient relationships, and oral health-related quality of life: a structural equation modelling', *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*, 21(1), pp. 1–8. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12955-023-02214-x>

Soss, M.J., Coulson, N.S. and Davies, E.B. (2022) 'Exploring social support in an online support community for Tourette Syndrome and Tic Disorders: analysis of postings', *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 24(10), pp. 1–9. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/34403>

Stangvaltaite-Mouhat, L. *et al.* (2023) 'Web-based interventions reduced dental anxiety among adults in Lithuania and Norway: a pilot study', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(4), pp. 3343–3343.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20043343>

Statista (2024) *Digital users worldwide 2020*. Available at:

<https://www.statista.com/statistics/617136/digital-population-worldwide> (Accessed: 2 September 2024).

Stein, D.J. *et al.* (2017) 'The cross-national epidemiology of social anxiety disorder: data from the World Mental Health Survey Initiative', *BMC Medicine*, 15(1), pp. 1–21. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-017-0889-2>

Stieger, S., Lewetz, D. and Willinger, D. (2023) 'Face-to-face more important than digital communication for mental health during the pandemic', *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), pp. 1–12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-34957-4>

Strand, M., Eng, L.S. and Gammon, D. (2020) 'Combining online and offline peer support groups in community mental health care settings: a qualitative study of service users' experiences', *International Journal of Mental Health Systems*, 14(1), pp. 1–12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13033-020-00370-x>

Strieder, A.P. *et al.* (2019) 'Is there a relationship of negative oral health beliefs with dental fear and anxiety regarding diverse dental patient groups? A systematic review and meta-analysis', *Clinical Oral Investigations*, 23(9), pp. 3613–3621.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00784-018-2786-2>

Sugiura, L., Wiles, R. and Pope, C. (2017) 'Ethical challenges in online research: public/private perceptions', *Research Ethics*, 13(3-4), pp. 184–199.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1747016116650720>

Sukumaran, I., Taylor, S. and Thomson, W.M. (2020) 'The prevalence and impact of dental anxiety among adult New Zealanders', *International Dental Journal*, 71(2), pp. 1–5. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/idj.12613>

Sun, I.G. *et al.* (2024) 'Global prevalence of early childhood dental fear and anxiety: a systematic review and meta-analysis', *Journal of Dentistry*, 142, pp. 1–10. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdent.2024.104841>

Svensson, L., Hakeberg, M. and Wide, U. (2016) 'Dental anxiety, concomitant factors and change in prevalence over 50 years', *Community Dental Health*, 33(2), pp. 1–6. doi:https://doi.org/10.1922/CDH_3694Svensson06

Svensson, L., Hakeberg, M. and Wide, U. (2018) 'Dental pain and oral health-related quality of life in individuals with severe dental anxiety', *Acta Odontologica Scandinavica*, 76(6), pp. 401–406. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/00016357.2018.1473892>

Szeto, M.D. *et al.* (2021) 'Social media in dermatology and an overview of popular social media platforms', *Current Dermatology Reports*, 10, pp. 97–104. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13671-021-00343-4>

Tang, J., Yu, G. and Yao, X. (2021) 'Emotional contagion in the online depression community', *Healthcare*, 9(12), pp. 1–14. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9121609>

Tannenbaum, C., Greaves, L. and Graham, I.D. (2016) 'Why sex and gender matter in implementation research', *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 16(1), pp. 1–14. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-016-0247-7>

The British Psychological Society (2021) *Ethics guidelines for internet-mediated research*. Available at: <https://explore.bps.org.uk/content/report-guideline/bpsrep.2021.rep155> (Accessed: 26 July 2024).

Thomson, W.M. *et al.* (2009) 'Trajectories of dental anxiety in a birth cohort', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 37(3), pp. 209–219.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0528.2009.00473.x>

Thomson, W.M. *et al.* (1996) 'Dental anxiety among Australians', *International Dental Journal*. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9147119/> (Accessed: 20 August 2024).

Tizzoni, R. *et al.* (2020) 'A case series analysing patients with dental anxiety: a patient-centered model based on psychological profiling', *F1000Research*, 8, pp. 1–16. doi:<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.20712.2>

Toon, M. *et al.* (2019) 'An analysis of stress and burnout in UK general dental practitioners: subdimensions and causes', *British Dental Journal*, 226(2), pp. 125–130.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.bdj.2019.46>

Uziel, N. *et al.* (2019) 'Management of the dentally anxious patient: the dentist's perspective', *Oral Health and Preventive Dentistry*, 17(1), pp. 35–41.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.3290/j.ohpd.a41985>

Vainauskiene, V. and Vaitkiene, R. (2021) 'Enablers of patient knowledge empowerment for self-management of chronic disease: an integrative review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(5), pp. 1–24.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18052247>

Valastro, M.L., Bono, L.K. and Gurenlian, J.R. (2024) 'Dentally anxious patients' perceptions of oral health care', *American Dental Hygienists' Association*. Available at: <https://jdh.adha.org/content/98/4/9.short> (Accessed: 23 August 2024).

Valdes-Stauber, J. and Hummel, K. (2021) 'The relationship between dental anxiety and other kinds of anxiety: a naturalistic, cross-sectional and comparative study', *BMC Psychology*, 9(1), pp. 1–10. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-021-00684-6>

van Gastel, D. *et al.* (2023) 'Social support among women with potential Essure-related complaints: analysis of Facebook group content', *JMIR formative research*, 7, pp. 1–8. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/32592>

Vermaire, J.H., de Jongh, A. and Aartman, I.H.A. (2008) 'Dental anxiety and quality of life: the effect of dental treatment', *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology*, 36(5), pp. 409–416. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0528.2007.00416.x>

Verster, J.C. *et al.* (2019) 'Advantages and limitations of naturalistic study designs and their implementation in alcohol hangover research', *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 8(12), pp. 1–10. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm8122160>

Vika, M. *et al.* (2008) 'Fear of blood, injury, and injections, and its relationship to dental anxiety and probability of avoiding dental treatment among 18-year-olds in Norway', *International Journal of Paediatric Dentistry*, 18(3), pp. 163–169. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-263x.2007.00904.x>

Vriens, E. and van Ingen, E. (2017) 'Does the rise of the Internet bring erosion of strong ties? Analyses of social media use and changes in core discussion networks', *New Media & Society*, 20(7), pp. 2432–2449. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444817724169>

- Walsh, C.A. and Al Achkar, M. (2021) 'A qualitative study of online support communities for lung cancer survivors on targeted therapies', *Supportive Care in Cancer*, pp. 1–8. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00520-021-05989-1>
- Wang, Y. *et al.* (2023) 'Social support, oral health knowledge, attitudes, practice, self-efficacy and oral health-related quality of life in Chinese college students', *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), pp. 1–10. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-39658-6>
- Wardenaar, K.J. *et al.* (2017) 'The cross-national epidemiology of specific phobia in the World Mental Health Surveys', *Psychological Medicine*, 47(10), pp. 1744–1760. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0033291717000174>
- Watts, F.M. and Finkenstaedt-Quinn, S.A. (2021) 'The current state of methods for establishing reliability in qualitative chemistry education research articles', *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, pp. 1–15. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1039/d1rp00007a>
- Weber, R. (1990) 'Introduction', *Basic content analysis*. 2nd edn. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc, pp. 9–14.
- Weiner, A.A. and Sheehan, D.V. (1990) 'Etiology of dental anxiety: psychological trauma or CNS chemical imbalance?', *General dentistry*. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2376317/> (Accessed: 19 August 2024).
- Weintraub, J.A. *et al.* (2019) 'Factors associated with becoming edentulous in the US Health and Retirement Study', *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 67(11), pp. 2318–2324. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/jgs.16079>
- Winkler, C. *et al.* (2023) 'Impact of dental anxiety on dental care routine and oral-health-related quality of life in a German adult population—a cross-sectional study', *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 12(16), pp. 5291–5291. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12165291>

Winzelberg, A. (1997) 'The analysis of an electronic support group for individuals with eating disorders', *Computers in Human Behavior*, 13(3), pp. 393–407.
doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0747-5632\(97\)00016-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0747-5632(97)00016-2)

Wong, M. and Lytle, W.R. (1991) 'A comparison of anxiety levels associated with root canal therapy and oral surgery treatment', *Journal of Endodontics*, 17(9), pp. 461–465.
doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0099-2399\(07\)80138-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0099-2399(07)80138-5)

Wong, N.S.M. *et al.* (2022) 'Qualitative evaluation of YouTube videos on dental fear, anxiety and phobia', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(1), pp. 1–17. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20010750>

Wright, K. (2016) 'Communication with online social support groups for individuals facing health concerns: a review of theory and research on supportive interactions and their implications online for health outcomes', *Review of Communication Research*. Available at: <https://rcommunicationr.org/index.php/rcr/article/view/42> (Accessed: 4 March 2024).

Wright, W.J.A. *et al.* (2024) 'Exploring the types of social support exchanged by survivors of pediatric stroke and their families in an online peer support community: qualitative thematic analysis', *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 26(1), pp. 1–12.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/49440>

Wu, J.-J. *et al.* (2019) 'Impact of emotional support, informational support, and norms of reciprocity on trust toward the medical aesthetic community: the moderating effect of core self-evaluations', *Interactive Journal of Medical Research*, 8(1), pp. 1–12.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/11750>

Yamada, D. *et al.* (2010) 'Lack of neurotensin type 1 receptor facilitates contextual fear memory depending on the memory strength', *Pharmacology Biochemistry and Behavior*, 96(3), pp. 363–369. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pbb.2010.06.007>

Yokota, K. *et al.* (2020) 'The extent and nature of dental anxiety in Australians experiencing homelessness', *Health & Social Care in the Community*, 28(6), pp. 1–10. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/hsc.13056>

Yuchao, W., Ying, Z. and Liao, Z. (2021) 'Health privacy information self-disclosure in online health community', *Frontiers in Public Health*, 8, pp. 1–15. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.602792>

Yusof, M.Y.P.M., Teo, C.H. and Ng, C.J. (2022) 'Electronic informed consent criteria for research ethics review: a scoping review', *BMC Medical Ethics*, 23(1), pp. 1–11. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-022-00849-x>

Yusuf, H., Golkari, A. and Kaddour, S. (2023) 'Oral health of people experiencing homelessness in London: a mixed methods study', *BMC Public Health*, 23(1), pp. 1–11. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-16648-x>

Zahra, F. *et al.* (2024) 'Place of forums in online communication through an LMS platform', *World Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology and Sciences*, 11(1), pp. 96–104. doi:<https://doi.org/10.30574/wjaets.2024.11.1.0042>

Zapf, A. *et al.* (2016) 'Measuring inter-rater reliability for nominal data – which coefficients and confidence intervals are appropriate?', *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 16(1), pp. 1–10. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-016-0200-9>

Zhang, S., Li, J. and Hu, X. (2022) 'Peer support interventions on quality of life, depression, anxiety, and self-efficacy among patients with cancer: a systematic review

and meta-analysis', *Patient Education and Counseling*, 105(11), pp. 3213–3224.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2022.07.008>

Zhou, Y. *et al.* (2022) 'Genome-wide scan of dental fear and anxiety nominates novel genes', *Journal of Dental Research*, 101(12), pp. 1526–1536.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/00220345221105226>

Zimmerman, M.A. (1995) 'Psychological empowerment: issues and illustrations', *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 23(5), pp. 581–599.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02506983>